

QUANTUM RANDOM WALKS

Decoherence and sub-ballistic dynamics

BACHELOR THESIS

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Abstract

In this thesis we study the dynamical properties of quantum random walks. Specifically, we are interested in the propagation behaviour and the asymptotic position distribution of a particle undergoing a quantum random walk. The perturbation method developed by Ahlbrecht et al. [1], [2] provides an efficient tool for studying both coherent and decoherent quantum random walks. The thesis consists of 3 parts. Firstly, we provide a detailed description of quantum random walks with a focus on position measurement. Starting at the standard axioms of quantum mechanics, we translate the problem of measuring the position of a quantum particle undergoing time evolution into a problem of computing the asymptotic limit of a sequence of characteristic functions. Secondly, we outline the main ideas of the perturbation method and discuss how fluctuations in the choice of time evolution operator generically slows the propagation behaviour from ballistic to diffusive spreading. Finally, we apply the method to finite quantum Lévy walks to demonstrate an example of a decoherent quantum walk with diffusive propagation behaviour. We show how the variance of the position distribution diverges in the limit where we go from finite to infinite Lévy walks. This indicates that infinite Lévy walks will exhibit faster than diffusive propagation behaviour albeit the presence of decoherence.

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1 Introduction

A random walk is a stochastic process describing the path resulting from a series of random steps in some mathematical space. In classical computer science, random walks provide an important tool for randomized algorithms applied mainly to search and sampling problems, but also other areas such as link prediction, computer vision and semi-supervised learning [12]. The widespread and efficient use of classical random walks motivate the study of the quantum mechanical analogue, namely the quantum random walks. Ever since the discovery of Shor's quantum algorithm for polynomial-time integer factorization [10], the field of quantum computing and algorithms has been studied extensively and have shown promise in providing speed-ups compared to their classical counterparts in computer science. Among the first was Grover's algorithm for unstructured search, providing a quadratic speed-up [5]. Quantum random walks have been a key component in the development of powerful new quantum search algorithms as outlined by Venegas-Andraca [11]. The applications even go as far as a quantum mechanical version of Google's PageRank algorithm [7].

From a physics point of view, quantum random walks describe the dynamics of a quantum particle restricted to discrete time and space. It turns out, that for the particle to move randomly under unitary time evolution, it requires an internal degree of freedom [3]. A particular class of quantum walks are the so called coin-shift walks. Here, the time evolution consists of a coin operator acting solely on the internal degree of freedom followed by a shift operator conditioned on the internal degree of freedom. An example could be a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ particle moving freely on the integers. Every time step consists of a rotation of the spin followed by a shift right and left where the probabilities depend on the spin up and down along a given axis. After t time steps a measurement of the particle's position will yield a random variable on the integers Q_t . What we are interested in here is the evolution of the position distribution and especially how the distribution scales with time. This scaling determines certain features that are essential for the efficiency of the quantum algorithms developed with the quantum walks. These features include the *hitting time*, the expected number of steps before a certain point is reached, and the *mixing rate*, which is a measure for the rate of convergence towards an asymptotic distribution [11]. It is well known that a simple classical random walk on the integers converges in distribution to a normal distribution with variance scaling as the square-root of time (see Theorem 21.1 in [6]). This type of spreading is called *diffusive*. As we will see, quantum walks can experience faster propagation behaviour. The standard example is the quantum walk on the integers using the unitary Hadamard coin operator. This scales linearly in time [1], which we call *ballistic* spreading. We will study how fluctuations in the choice of time evolution operator can cause the propagation behaviour of quantum random walks to change from ballistic to diffusive. Additionally, we will study quantum Lévy walks both in the finite and infinite case. We provide support for the hypothesis that the infinite quantum Lévy walks will exhibit behaviour somewhere between diffusive and ballistic.

2 Preliminaries

We wish to find the long time limit of the position distribution of a quantum particle with an internal degree of freedom undergoing a quantum random walk on a discrete lattice. For this it turns out to be very useful to represent position measurements as a random variable and draw on results from measure theory. A central result from measure theory is that a sequence of random variables converge in distribution if and only if their characteristic functions converge pointwise. In Section 3 we will discuss how to find the limit of this sequence of characteristic functions using the perturbation method from [1] and [2]. The aim of this section is to derive the measure theoretic representation of position measurements of quantum random walks from the axioms of quantum mechanics. This will lead us to the sequence of characteristic functions considered in [1] and [2].

2.1 The system

A quantum random walk describes the time evolution of a quantum particle in discrete time and space. We will use \mathbb{Z}^s as the underlying lattice on which the particle moves. The corresponding Hilbert space is therefore the space of square summable functions on \mathbb{Z}^s denoted by $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s)$. The internal degree of freedom will be finite and is represented by a vector in a finite dimensional complex vector space \mathcal{K} . Often, we will take $\mathcal{K} = \mathbb{C}^2$ and consider particles with a spin- $\frac{1}{2}$. The combined Hilbert space, describing both the external and internal degrees of freedom, is therefore $\mathcal{H} = \ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s) \otimes \mathcal{K}$. This Hilbert space is separable so we can consider the orthonormal basis $\{|x\rangle \otimes |i\rangle\}_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s, i \in I}$. Here, I is the index set $\{1, 2, \dots, \dim \mathcal{K}\}$. Note that we will use Dirac notation throughout this thesis. The state of the particle can be represented by a density operator ρ (i.e. a positive and normalized trace-class operator) on $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s) \otimes \mathcal{K}$. Note that positivity implies that ρ is also self-adjoint and bounded. The set of bounded operators on the Hilbert space \mathcal{H} will be denoted $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$.

2.2 Position Measurement

Let ρ be a general mixed state given as a sum the pure states $|\psi_j\rangle\langle\psi_j|$, each with a corresponding probability λ_j such that

$$\rho = \sum_j \lambda_j |\psi_j\rangle\langle\psi_j| \quad (1)$$

where each vector $|\psi_j\rangle \in \mathcal{H}$ can be written in the basis $\{|x\rangle \otimes |i\rangle\}_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s, i \in I}$ as

$$|\psi_j\rangle = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s, i \in I} \psi_{x,i}^j |x\rangle \otimes |i\rangle, \quad \psi_{x,i}^j \in \mathbb{C} \quad (2)$$

From the axioms of quantum mechanics it follows that the probability that a position measure-

ment of a pure state $|\psi_j\rangle\langle\psi_j|$ yields the value $x' \in \mathbb{Z}^s$ is $\sum_{i \in I} |\psi_{x',i}^j|^2$. For a mixed state ρ of the form (1), the probability of finding the particle at x' is therefore

$$\text{Prob}(x') = \sum_j \lambda_j \sum_{i \in I} |\psi_{x',i}^j|^2 \quad (3)$$

We wish to formulate this as a probability measure for any density operator. The power set $\mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s)$ is a known σ -algebra on \mathbb{Z}^s so we can choose the pair $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$ as our measure space. Consider the map $P : \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s) \mapsto \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ with $P(X) = \sum_{x \in X} |x\rangle\langle x| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}$ for every $X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s)$. We prove in Appendix A that for any density operator $\rho \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$, the map $\mu : X \mapsto \langle P(X) | \rho \rangle_{HS} = \text{tr} P(X) \rho$ defines the unique probability measure on $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$ which satisfies the axiom in Equation 3. Note that we use $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle_{HS}$ to denote the Hilbert-Schmidt inner product.

2.3 The position random variable and its characteristic function

We will see that this measure theoretic context to the standard quantum theory provided here allows for a rigorous analysis of the scaled position distribution and its characteristic function. Let the particle be in the state ρ_t after $t \in \mathbb{N}$ time steps. The corresponding probability measure is given by $\mu_t(X) = \text{tr} \rho_t P(X)$ for any $X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s)$. As we have shown, this function always defines a probability measure. We can then define a sequence of position random variables $\{Q_t\}_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$ by the maps $Q_t : (\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s), \mu_t) \mapsto (\mathbb{R}^s, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s), \mu_t^{Q_t})$ given by $Q_t(x) = x$ for every $t \in \mathbb{N}$. These can be thought of as the random variable equivalent of the position operator $Q = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} x |x\rangle\langle x| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}$.

Here $\mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s)$ is the Borel σ -algebra on \mathbb{R}^s and $\mu_t^{Q_t}$ is the pull-back measure defined by the pre-image of Q_t such that $\mu_t^{Q_t}(A) = \mu_t(Q_t^{-1}(A))$ for every $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s)$. This allows us to consider the probability that a position measurement yields a value in the subset A of \mathbb{R}^s . At time t this is indeed given by the pull-back measure as $\text{Prob}(x \in A) = \mu_t(A \cap \mathbb{Z}^s) = \mu_t(Q_t^{-1}(A)) = \mu_t^{Q_t}(A)$. The reason we map the probabilities into \mathbb{R}^s this way is to allow us to consider the scaled position random variable $Q_t/t^\alpha : x \mapsto x/t^\alpha$ for any $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$. We denote the pull-back measures of these scaled random variables by $\mu_{t,\alpha}$. With this, the subset $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s)$, has measure $\mu_{t,\alpha}(\{x : x \in A\}) = \mu_t(\{x : x/t^\alpha \in A \cap \mathbb{Z}^s\})$. As an example, consider the the subset $[1, 2)$ with measure $\mu_{t,\alpha}([1, 2)) = \mu_t([t^\alpha, 2t^\alpha))$. We say that the particle propagates as t^α if the sequence of measures $\mu_{t,\alpha}$ converge weakly to a non-trivial limit. By weak convergence we mean that the sequence of integrals over any test function with respect to the measures converge (see Appendix D.1). Intuitively, this captures the idea that the particles position distribution spreads out in time at a rate that is proportional to t^α . We can then characterise diffusive propagation behaviour as the case $\alpha = 1/2$ and similarly the dynamics are ballistic if $\alpha = 1$. Note that for any exponent $\beta > \alpha$, the measures $\mu_{t,\beta}$ will clearly also converge weakly, but to a point measure at the origin. We therefore consider the minimal α for which $\mu_{t,\alpha}$ converges weakly. When studying weak convergence of pull-back measures it is useful to consider the characteristic functions of the corresponding random variables. In Appendix D we provide

an overview of the properties of characteristic functions that are important in the context of quantum random walks. Additionally, we show how one can extract the position distribution given the characteristic function. This result is taken from [2], but we provide further details necessary for the level of this thesis. Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$ be a probability space. A general random variable $T : (\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu) \mapsto (\mathbb{R}^s, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s), \mu^T)$ is in one-to-one correspondence with its characteristic function C_T given by

$$C_T(\lambda) = \langle e^{i\lambda \cdot T} \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} e^{i\lambda \cdot x} d\mu^T(x), \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^s \quad (4)$$

Firstly, note that the scaling behaviour is given by $C_{\beta T}(\lambda) = \langle e^{i\lambda \cdot \beta T} \rangle = \langle e^{i\beta \lambda \cdot T} \rangle = C_T(\beta \lambda)$ for any $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$. Let $\varepsilon = \varepsilon(t) \in \mathbb{R}$ be a scaling parameter satisfying $\varepsilon(t) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. The characteristic function of the scaled position random variable thus satisfies $C_{\varepsilon Q_t}(\lambda) = C_{Q_t}(\varepsilon \lambda)$. It now follows that

$$\begin{aligned} C_{Q_t}(\varepsilon \lambda) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot x} d\mu_t^{Q_t}(x) = \int_{\mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q_t(x)} d\mu_t(x) = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q_t(x)} \text{tr } \rho_t P(\{x\}) \\ &= \text{tr} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot x} \rho_t P(\{x\}) = \text{tr } \rho_t \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot x} P(\{x\}) = \text{tr } \rho_t e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} x P(\{x\})} = \text{tr } \rho_t e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q} \end{aligned}$$

Here the second equality follows from the transformation rule (Thm 15.1 in Schilling) [9], the third from \mathbb{Z}^s being countable, the fourth by the definition Q_t and linearity of the trace, the fifth and sixth from P being a projection operator with $P(\{x\})P(\{y\}) = P(\{x\})\delta_{x,y}$ and the last equality follows from the definitions of P and Q .

As Q is self-adjoint, the operator $e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q}$ is unitary and thus norm preserving. The operator norm is therefore equal to 1 implying that $e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. Unitarity also implies that it is a Hilbert-Schmidt operator. This means that the characteristic function is well-defined as the inner product $C_{Q_t}(\varepsilon \lambda) = \langle \rho_t | e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q} \rangle_{HS}$ or equivalently we can think of it as the expectation value of the operator $e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q}$ at time t in the standard quantum mechanical sense.

2.4 Time evolution

The type of quantum walks, we will consider here are the so-called *coin-shift* walks. The basic idea is to model a quantum analogue of a classical random walk, where a coin is flipped at every time step deciding whether the walker takes a step left or right. Coin-shift walks consist of a coin matrix acting solely on the internal degree of freedom of the particle and a shift operator moving the particle around on the underlying lattice depending on the result of applying the coin matrix. The standard example is the Hadamard walk in one dimension. We consider a particle moving on the integers with two internal degrees of freedom corresponding to spin- $\frac{1}{2}$. At every time step, the particle is first shifted by the standard shift operator, which we denote throughout this thesis by S . This acts by shifting the spin-up part to the right and the spin-down part to the left. In the basis $\{|x, i\rangle_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s, i=0,1}$

$$S = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |x+1\rangle\langle x| \otimes |1\rangle\langle 1| + |x-1\rangle\langle x| \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0| \quad (5)$$

Following the shift, the spin of the particle at every position is rotated by the unitary Hadamard coin matrix H , where

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The total time evolution is therefore defined in the Schrödinger picture by the operator $(\mathbb{1} \otimes H) \cdot S$ such that a density operator ρ is mapped to $[(\mathbb{1} \otimes H) \cdot S] \rho [(\mathbb{1} \otimes H) \cdot S]^*$. In general, we will work in the Heisenberg picture with quantum channels as the general framework for time evolution. The time evolution will be given by a linear, unital, completely positive and local map $\mathbf{W} : \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H}) \mapsto \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. \mathbf{W} is the adjoint of the Schrödinger time evolution operator, which acts on the states directly. Any quantum channel \mathbf{W} admits a Kraus decomposition (i.e. a set of operators $\{K_i\}$ with $\sum_i K_i^* K_i = \mathbb{1}$ such that $\mathbf{W}(A) = \sum_i K_i^* A K_i$) and in practice we will define \mathbf{W} by choosing a set of Kraus operators. For example, the Hadamard quantum walk is given in the Heisenberg picture by the single Kraus operator $K = (\mathbb{1} \otimes H) \cdot S$. For any time evolved state ρ_t and operator $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ we can exchange ρ_t with the state at time $t = 0$ in the sense that $\langle \rho_t | A \rangle_{HS} = \langle \rho_0 | \mathbf{W}^t(A) \rangle_{HS}$. The characteristic function of the scaled position random variable at time t is then given by

$$C_{\varepsilon Q_t}(\lambda) = \langle \rho_0 | \mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}) \rangle_{HS} = \text{tr} \rho_0 \mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}) \quad (7)$$

By Lévy's continuity theorem, the sequence of scaled position random variables $\{\varepsilon Q_t\}_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$ converge in distribution to a random variable \tilde{Q} if and only if the characteristic functions $C_{\varepsilon Q_t}(\lambda)$ converge pointwise to a function $C(\lambda)$ which is continuous at the origin. Additionally, $C(\lambda)$ is the unique characteristic function of \tilde{Q} . The problem of finding the asymptotic scaled position distribution for a quantum random walk described by the time evolution operator \mathbf{W} reduces therefore to computing the pointwise limit of $\text{tr} \rho_0 \mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q})$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$. As the implication goes both ways, we also use this to show that the random variables *do not* converge in distribution. This will be a central argument in Section 4.3.

3 Perturbation Method

In this section we will outline the perturbation method developed by Ahlbrecht, Vogts, Werner and Werner [1]. This method is specifically designed to compute the long time limit of $\text{tr} \rho_0 \mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q})$ for a given scaling ε . The purpose of this section is therefore to explain how and why we can apply the perturbation method to our model of Lévy walks, as described in Section 4. Additionally, we aim to emphasise the exact nature of the momentum space representations of both operators and channels drawing on Appendix B.

3.1 Coherent quantum walks

We start here by restricting the set of walks to be translation invariant quantum walks. Translation invariance means that the time evolution operator is homogeneous in space and therefore commutes with the translation operators (see Appendix A.4) τ_x for any $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$. Hence, we consider channels \mathbf{W} satisfying $\mathbf{W} \circ \tau_x = \tau_x \circ \mathbf{W}$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$. In fact, for this thesis we will only consider walks defined by channels represented by a set of translation invariant Kraus operators though the method is more general. This is clearly a stronger condition than translation invariance of \mathbf{W} and following [1] we say that these walks exhibit no momentum transfer. Locality means that the particle can only move a finite distance in a single time step. Let $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}^s$ and $M \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$ and consider the general matrix element $|x\rangle\langle y| \otimes M$ of an operator in $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. For any vectors $\psi, \phi \in \mathcal{K}$ we require that $\langle k \otimes \phi | \mathbf{W}(|x\rangle\langle y| \otimes M) | l \otimes \psi \rangle = 0$ whenever $\max\{|k-x|, |l-y|\} > c$ for a given $c \in \mathbb{N}$. Clearly, the Hadamard walk is translation invariant as we apply the same coin matrix to every position and the shift operator simply shifts left and right independently of the location on the integers. Additionally, it shifts left and right by one lattice site so it is also local as the condition is fulfilled for $c = 1$. We mention these statements as intuitive facts here and refer to Appendix F.2 for the rigorous proofs.

Let us define the ε -dependent map $\phi_\varepsilon : \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H}) \mapsto \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ by $\phi_\varepsilon(A) = A e^{i\lambda\varepsilon Q}$ for any $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. This is clearly a bijection with the inverse defined by $\phi_\varepsilon^{-1}(A) = A e^{-i\lambda\varepsilon Q}$. With this we define the perturbed channel: $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon = \phi_\varepsilon^{-1} \circ \mathbf{W} \circ \phi_\varepsilon$. From this it follows that $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t = \phi_\varepsilon^{-1} \circ \mathbf{W}^t \circ \phi_\varepsilon$ and thus $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t(\mathbf{1}) e^{i\varepsilon\lambda Q} = \mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda Q})$. The point is that in the limit as ε goes to zero, we can replace $\mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda Q})$ in the characteristic function by $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t(\mathbf{1})$. This follows from the facts that \mathbf{W} is bounded in operator norm by 1 and that ϕ_ε approaches the identity as ε goes to zero (see (4.17) in [2]). The limiting characteristic function is therefore $C(\lambda) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \text{tr} \rho_0 \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t(\mathbf{1})$.

The identity, $\mathbf{1} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$, is clearly a translation invariant eigenvector of \mathbf{W} and we wish to apply a high power of the perturbed operator $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ to this. Now the perturbed operator also commutes with translations (see Appendix E.1) and this implies that both \mathbf{W} and $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ map translation invariant operators to translation invariant operators. We can therefore choose to restrict them to the subspace of $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ containing all translation invariant operators. Following [2], we denote this subspace by $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ and note that \mathbf{W} and $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ are endomorphisms on this subspace, which is in fact a Hilbert space itself [2]. As explained in Appendix B.2, operators in $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ can be represented in momentum space by integral kernels via the Fourier Transform. Operators in the subspace $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ are represented in momentum space by multiplication operators in the sense that their integral kernels are of the form $A(p)\delta(p-p')$, where $A(p)$ is simply a finite dimensional matrix in $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$. We can likewise represent superoperators acting on $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ in momentum space by maps between integral kernels. We show this and how they simplify when acting on translation invariant operators in Appendix B.5.

As explained in Appendix C.2, the trace of an operator in momentum space is found by integrating the diagonal of the integral kernel representing it. Specifically, since $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t(\mathbf{1})$ is translation invariant for all t , we can use Equation 94 from Appendix C.2 to express the trace as

$$\mathrm{tr} \rho_0 \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t(\mathbb{1}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \mathrm{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho_0(p, p) \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t \mathbb{1} \right)(p) \quad (8)$$

A crucial point is that when the Kraus operators of the channel $\mathbf{W} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s})$ are themselves translation invariant, then the time evolution in momentum space of an operator $A \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ depends only on the operator A at the single point p in the sense that $(\mathbf{W}A)(p) = \mathbf{W}(p)A(p)$. In other words, $(\mathbf{W}A)(p)$ does not depend on $A(p')$ at points $p' \neq p$ and we see that \mathbf{W} acts directly as a pointwise map on the multiplication operator $A(p) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$ representing A . This is indeed the reason why we refer to this condition as the time evolution experiencing no momentum transfer and the important observation is that we can now fix a point p and carry out the analysis of computing the limit of $\left(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t \mathbb{1} \right)(p)$ pointwise. As an example of how a quantum channel without momentum transfer acts in momentum space looks we have computed the Fourier transform of the standard shift operator S in Appendix F.2. The result is that

$$S(p) = \mathcal{F}S\mathcal{F}^* = \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

and the total time evolution of the Hadamard walk in momentum space is now simply $(\mathbf{W}A)(p) = (HS(p))^* A(p) (HS(p))$

In general, if the quantum walk \mathbf{W} is given by the set of translation invariant Kraus operators $\{K_\alpha\}$ and $A \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$, then the time evolution in momentum space is given by $(\mathbf{W}A)(p) = \mathbf{W}(p)A(p) = \sum_\alpha K_\alpha^*(p)A(p)K_\alpha(p)$ and by straightforward computation (see Appendix E.2), the perturbed operator satisfies $(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A)(p) = \sum_\alpha K_\alpha^*(p)A(p)K_\alpha(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$. Here $K_\alpha(p)$ denotes the p -dependent multiplication operator in $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$ representing the operator $K_\alpha \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$. Hence, the no momentum transfer condition allows for finite dimensional perturbation theory in terms of these p -dependent Kraus matrices. The question that remains is under what conditions the eigenvalue branches are analytic in ε . We are of course specifically interested in the eigenvalue and eigenprojection corresponding to the eigenvector $\mathbb{1}$. Locality implies that each matrix element of the Kraus operators in momentum space is given by a finite degree trigonometric polynomial [2] so $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ is indeed analytic in ε as an operator. Non-analyticity of the eigenvalue branches can therefore only arise at degenerate points or if different eigenvalues cross each other close to $\varepsilon = 0$, such that the choice of branch is then no longer unique [2].

A unitary quantum walk consists of a single translation invariant Kraus operator such that $(\mathbf{W}A)(p) = W^*(p)A(p)W(p)$ for some p -dependent unitary matrix $W \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$. The perturbed operator is thus $(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A)(p) = W^*(p)A(p)W(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$ and it turns out that for almost every $p \in [-\pi, \pi]^s$, we can choose a neighbourhood $G \subset \mathbb{C}$ around the origin such that the eigenvalues and eigenprojections of $W(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$ are indeed analytic for $\varepsilon \in G$ (see Proposition 4.5.5 in [2]). The set of non-analytic points (i.e. the set of degenerate points) is in fact finite and therefore a null set with respect to the Lebesgue measure. The characteristic function is therefore not affected if we neglect these points. At analytic points, one can compute the limit of

$(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t \mathbf{1})(p) = (W^*(p)W(p + \varepsilon\lambda))^t$ directly from the spectral decomposition of W . We find that unitary walks always scale ballistically - i.e. $\alpha = 1$ provides a non-trivial limit for the scaled position distribution Q_t/t^α . We can even find an expression for the scaled position distribution. The details of all this are provided in Appendix F along with an example where we explicitly compute the asymptotic position distribution of the Hadamard walk.

3.2 Decoherent quantum walks

So far we have assumed that the time evolution operator does not change with time - i.e. at each time step the same quantum channel \mathbf{W} is applied. We will now generalise and allow for fluctuations in the choice of time evolution operator. This generalisation is indeed necessary for how we will model quantum Lévy walks in the next section. The general method of decoherent walks is described thoroughly by Ahlbrecht et al. in [1] and [2].

Following [1] and [2] we consider an external and classical control process which, at each time step, picks a walk from a finite set of translation invariant walks. Let Γ be a finite index set and let \mathbf{V}_γ be a translation invariant quantum walk for each $\gamma \in \Gamma$. The control process is taken to be Markovian such that at each time step the probability of picking the walk \mathbf{V}_γ only depends on the walk picked at the previous time step. The total time evolution therefore consists of a step updating the probabilities followed by a step applying the walks. In the coherent case, we found that if the particle was in the state ρ_t after t time steps, then the probability of a position measurement yielding a value in $X \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^s$ was given by the measure $\mu(X) = \text{tr } \rho_t P(X)$. This is clearly not the case anymore as the state of the particle after t time steps is now dependent on which walks the control process has chosen at each time step. Hence, we need to incorporate the probabilities of the Markovian control process into the position probability measure. A natural way to do this is to consider observables as bounded maps from Γ to $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. Following [2] we thus consider the space of observables as $\ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ and the time evolution will be an operator thereon. The background for this, and how it fits into our picture of modelling time evolution as a sequence of random variables and deducing the characteristic functions from there is explained in Appendix G.1. The argument is similar to that of Section 2, except that the total time evolution is now defined pointwise on an observable A as

$$(\mathbf{W}A)(\gamma) = \sum_{\eta \in \Gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \mathbf{V}_\eta(A(\eta)), \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma \quad (10)$$

where the non-negative numbers $\{\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta}\}_{\gamma,\eta \in \Gamma}$ satisfy $\sum_{\eta \in \Gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} = 1$ for any $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Additionally, we show that the characteristic function of the position random variable at time t is given by (194), which states that

$$C_{Q_t}(\lambda) = \sum_{\gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma} \text{tr } \rho_0 (\mathbf{W}^t e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q})(\gamma) \quad (11)$$

where we now consider $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}$ as the map $\eta \mapsto e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}$ for all $\eta \in \Gamma$ and \mathbf{m}_γ are non-negative with $\sum_\gamma \mathbf{m}_\gamma = 1$. \mathbf{m}_γ is the probability of picking the walk \mathbf{V}_γ at time $t = 0$, which we choose freely to initialise the Markov process

For each of the quantum walks \mathbf{V}_γ we can again define a corresponding perturbed operator $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma,\varepsilon} = \phi_\varepsilon^{-1} \circ \mathbf{V}_\gamma \circ \phi_\varepsilon$ and the total perturbed operator acts by $(\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A)(\gamma) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma,\varepsilon}(A(\eta))$. The perturbed operator raised to the power t thus consists of different combinations of the walks \mathbf{V}_γ - i.e. operator products of the form $\mathbf{V}_{\gamma_t} \circ \dots \circ \mathbf{V}_{\gamma_1}$. Since we use the same similarity transform for all $\gamma \in \Gamma$, the desired relation $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma_t,\varepsilon} \circ \dots \circ \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma_1,\varepsilon} = \phi_\varepsilon^{-1} \circ \mathbf{V}_{\gamma_t} \circ \dots \circ \mathbf{V}_{\gamma_1} \circ \phi_\varepsilon$ still holds. Let $\mathbb{1}_\Gamma$ denote the map $\gamma \mapsto \mathbb{1}_\mathcal{H}$ as an element of the observable space. It now follows that, as in the coherent case, $(\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t \mathbb{1}_\Gamma)(\gamma) e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} = (\mathbf{W}^t e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q})(\gamma)$ for all $\gamma \in \Gamma$, where the factor $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}$ again approaches the identity in the limit as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$. Note that $\mathbb{1}_\Gamma$ is indeed an eigenvector with eigenvalue 1 of the unperturbed operator \mathbf{W} , as we can see by

$$(\mathbf{W}\mathbb{1}_\Gamma)(\gamma) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \mathbf{V}_\gamma(\mathbb{1}_\Gamma(\eta)) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \mathbf{V}_\gamma(\mathbb{1}_\mathcal{H}) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \mathbb{1}_\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{1}_\mathcal{H} \quad (12)$$

Let each of the walks \mathbf{V}_γ be implemented by a set of translation invariant Kraus operators $\{K_{\gamma,j}\}$. The operators \mathbf{V}_γ will then conserve momentum such that their momentum space representations act directly and pointwise on the multiplication operators representing the translation invariant operators $A \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ by $(\mathbf{V}_\gamma A)(p) = \sum_j K_{\gamma,j}^*(p) A(p) K_{\gamma,j}(p)$. We define translation invariant observables as mappings from Γ to $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ - e.g. $\eta \mapsto A(\eta) \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$. Exactly as in the coherent case, we restrict the operators \mathbf{W} and $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ to the subset of $\ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ consisting of the translation invariant observables. Following [2] we denote this subspace by $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s,\Gamma}$. For the remaining part of this section, A will denote a translation invariant observable. We know that the perturbed operators can also be represented by maps directly on the multiplication operators with $(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma,\varepsilon} A(\eta))(p) = \sum_j K_{\gamma,j}^*(p) A(\eta, p) K_{\gamma,j}(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$. The action in momentum space of the total perturbed operator is therefore

$$(\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A)(\gamma, p) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma,\varepsilon}(p)(A(\eta, p)) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \sum_j K_{\gamma,j}^*(p) A(\eta, p) K_{\gamma,j}(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \quad (13)$$

This is a linear transformation of the p -dependent entries of the matrices $A(\eta, p)$. Each of the $|\Gamma|$ matrices has $(\dim \mathcal{K})^2$ entries, so we can express $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ as a finite dimensional p -dependent matrix with dimension $(\dim \mathcal{K})^2 \cdot |\Gamma|$. As in Section 3.1, the locality of the walks \mathbf{V}_γ implies that all the matrix entries of the Kraus operators $K_{\gamma,j}$ are finite trigonometric polynomials in each of the directions p_1, \dots, p_s so the entries of the matrix representation of $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ are analytic in ε . Hence, with the no-momentum transfer condition we can again fix a point p and apply perturbation theory. Following [2], the general idea is now to consider the Jordan normal form of the matrix representation of $\tilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$, which is

$$(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A)(p) = \sum_i (\mu_i(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_i(\varepsilon) + \mathbf{D}_i(\varepsilon)) (A(p)) \quad (14)$$

where \mathbf{P}_i , \mathbf{D}_i and μ_i are the ε -dependent eigenprojections, eigennilpotent operators and eigenvalues, respectively. Once again we are concerned with the eigenvalue branch corresponding to the eigenvector $\mathbb{1}_\Gamma$ with eigenvalue 1 of the unperturbed operator \mathbf{W} . We choose to let $i = 0$ represent this branch such that $\mu_0(0) = 1$ and $\mathbf{P}_0(0)\mathbb{1}_\Gamma = \mathbb{1}_\Gamma$. Informally, we wish to apply a high power of $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ to something that is almost an eigenvector. If $\mu_0(\varepsilon)$ and $\mathbf{P}_0(\varepsilon)$ are analytic in ε , we can expand these as power series and thereby compute the long time limit. As in the coherent case, $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ is analytic as an operator, so non-analyticity can only arise if the eigenvalue is degenerate or if it crosses other eigenvalues close to $\varepsilon = 0$. Following [2] we formulate this condition as the assumption that for almost all $p \in [-\pi, \pi]^s$ the eigenvalue $\mu_0(0) = 1$ is non-degenerate and all the other eigenvalues satisfy $|\mu_i(0)| < 1$. We call this *the eigenvalue assumption*. Proposition 4.5.11 in [2] shows that this assumption is satisfied when the decoherent quantum walk \mathbf{W} satisfies 3 criteria:

1. Let \mathbf{M} be the matrix with entries $\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta}$. For some power of \mathbf{M} all its entries are strictly positive.
2. For almost all p there is a density matrix $\bar{\rho}_p \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$ with non-zero eigenvalues that is invariant under time evolution in the sense that $\text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \bar{\rho}_p (\mathbf{V}_\gamma A)(p) = \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \bar{\rho}_p A$ for all $\gamma \in \Gamma$ and $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$.
3. For almost all p , and some $r \in \mathbb{N}$, the set of operator products $K_{\gamma_1, j_1} \cdots K_{\gamma_r, j_r}$ is such that only multiples of $\mathbb{1}$ commutes with all of them and its linear span contains the identity.

We refer to [2] for the proof. With this assumption all terms except the $i = 0$ term of the Jordan normal form in Equation 14 will vanish in the long time limit and we are left with $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} (\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \mathbb{1}_\Gamma)(p) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0^t(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_0(\varepsilon) (\mathbb{1}_\Gamma)$. See [2] for the proof of this and Appendix E.3 for an explanation at the level of this thesis. As t approaches infinity, ε will by definition go to zero such that $\mathbf{P}_0(\varepsilon)(\mathbb{1}_\Gamma)$ approaches $\mathbb{1}_\Gamma$. Hence, everything depends on the eigenvalue $\mu_0(\varepsilon)$ and we choose ε such that the limit of this exists. Turning back to the characteristic function in Equation 11, we know that we can replace $(\mathbf{W}^t e^{i\varepsilon\lambda Q})(\gamma)$ with $(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \mathbb{1}_\Gamma)(\gamma)$. As in the coherent case, we use the formula for the trace of translation invariant operators Equation 94 from Appendix C.2 to write the limiting characteristic function as

$$C(\lambda) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} C_{\varepsilon Q_t}(\lambda) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sum_\gamma \mathbf{m}_\gamma \text{tr} \rho_0 \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t \mathbb{1}_\Gamma \right) (\gamma) \quad (15)$$

$$= \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \sum_\gamma \frac{\mathbf{m}_\gamma}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho_0(p, p) \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t \mathbb{1}_\Gamma \right) (\gamma, p) \quad (16)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \left(\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0^t(\varepsilon) \right) \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho_0(p, p) \quad (17)$$

In the fourth equality we assume the scaling has been chosen such that the limit $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0^t(\varepsilon)$ exists. This together with the fact that the matrix elements of $(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t \mathbf{1}_\Gamma)(\gamma, p)$ must be bounded by 1, from which it follows that the integrand is bounded by 1, allows us to interchange the limit and integral by Lebesgue's dominated convergence theorem. A quick argument for why the matrix elements are bounded is that the similarity transforms have operator norm bounded by 1, since they multiply a unitary operator from the right, and hence each of the perturbed operators $\widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma, \varepsilon}$ must have operator norm bounded by the operator norm of the corresponding quantum walk \mathbf{V}_γ . It follows that the operator norm of $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ is bounded by 1 and so for any p the matrix elements must be bounded by 1.

The idea of [1] and [2] is now to find the limit of the eigenvalue by considering the eigenvalue equation $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(A_\varepsilon) = \mu_0(\varepsilon)A_\varepsilon$, where $A_\varepsilon \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K}, s, \Gamma}$ is the eigenvector with $A_0 = \mathbf{1}_\Gamma$. For the sake of clear notation we have omitted the p -dependence, but the point is still that we can do this for fixed p . For almost all p everything in this equation is analytic in ε so we can expand to second order and collect the terms to find equations for the first and second order terms in the expansion of the eigenvalue $\mu_0(\varepsilon) = 1 + \varepsilon\mu' + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2}\mu'' + \dots$ (see [2] or Appendix G.2). We summarise the results here. A key point is the existence of a p -dependent linear functional $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p$ on $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K}, s, \Gamma}$ acting by $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p : A \mapsto \sum_\eta \bar{\mathbf{m}}_\eta \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \bar{\rho}_{p, \eta} A(\eta, p)$, which is invariant under time evolution for almost all p in the sense that $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p(\mathbf{W}(A)) = \bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p(A)$ for every $A \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K}, s, \Gamma}$. We refer to [2] for the proof of the existence of $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p$ in general (Prop. 4.5.12) and to Appendix H.2 for the proof in context of quantum Lévy walks. This can be used to extract μ' and μ'' from the first and second order expansions of the eigenvalue equation [1], [2]. For completeness, we derive the formulae in Appendix G.2 and the result for μ' is given there by the Equations 208 and 209. We find that $\mu' = i\lambda \cdot v(p)$ where $v(p)$ is the function

$$v(p) = -i \sum_\eta \sum_j \bar{\mathbf{m}}_\eta \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \bar{\rho}_{p, \eta} K_{\eta, j}^*(p) \nabla K_{\eta, j}(p) \quad (18)$$

If this is non-zero, then ballistic scaling ($\varepsilon = 1/t$) will provide the non-trivial limit as

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0(1/t)^t = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{\mu'}{t} + o\left(\frac{1}{t^2}\right) \right)^{\frac{1}{t}} = e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} \quad (19)$$

In this case the sequence of characteristic functions converges towards

$$C(\lambda) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]} dp e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho_0(p, p) \quad (20)$$

and following [2], we have shown in Appendix D.2 that the scaled position distribution can be inferred directly from this with the result in Equation 109.

Here we take special interest in Bernoulli type quantum walks, where the Markov process is independent of the previous time step. In other words, the initial probabilities \mathbf{m}_η are kept as the constant probabilities throughout the time evolution. This is implemented by fixing

$\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} = \mathbf{m}_\eta$. As shown in [1], [2] (and Appendix G.3 for completeness), the problem of solving for the second order term in the expansion of $\mu_0(\varepsilon)$ reduces to a set of two equations. We introduce the average time evolution as $\mathbf{V}_0 = \sum_\gamma \mathbf{m}_\gamma \mathbf{V}_\gamma$ and likewise for the average perturbed operator (denoted with the tilde as always). As given in Equation 222, the second order is

$$\mu''(p) = \text{tr}_\mathcal{K} \bar{\rho}_p \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0''(\mathbf{1})(p) + 2 \text{tr}_\mathcal{K} \bar{\rho}_p \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0'(X)(p) \quad (21)$$

where X is an operator given indirectly by

$$\mathbf{V}_0(X) - X = i\lambda \cdot v\mathbf{1} - \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0'(\mathbf{1}) \quad (22)$$

If the first order is zero (i.e. $v(p) = 0$), then this will be the leading term in the expansion. More generally, if there is a constant drift in the system such that v is sharply peaked, then we can consider how the distribution spreads around this peak by changing the reference system. We find that diffusive scaling ($\varepsilon = 1/\sqrt{t}$) is the correct choice as the limit is

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0 \left(1/\sqrt{t} \right)^t = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(1 + \frac{\mu''(p)}{2t} + o\left(\frac{1}{t^{3/2}}\right) \right)^t = e^{\frac{1}{2}\mu''(p)} \quad (23)$$

A decoherent walk is unitary if all the operators \mathbf{V}_γ are unitarily implemented in the sense that there exists a single unitary operator K_γ such that $\mathbf{V}_\gamma(A) = K_\gamma^* A K_\gamma$. As shown in [1], these will experience this diffusive spreading behaviour around a constant drift, which may of course be zero. The conclusion is that coherent quantum random walks can scale linearly in time and thus quadratically faster than their classical counterpart. However, this advantage is fragile as the introduction of a classical random process into the quantum system will slow the spreading and remove this advantage. As an example to illustrate the powerful and sometimes counter intuitive effect of decoherence, we can consider a decoherent walk that picks with equal probability between the standard Hadamard walk and the Hadamard walk with step size 2 instead of 1. These are both unitary so the conclusion is that this will scale diffusively and not ballistically as the Hadamard walk alone.

4 Quantum Levy Walks

A natural question is if we can somehow combat this powerful slowing effect of decoherence. In other words, we wish to find a quantum walk where the quantum advantage prevails even in presence of decoherence. There has already been some numerical indications that Lévy type quantum random walks may show this behaviour [4], [8]. Here we aim to support this analytically by using the perturbation method to show an example of an infinite quantum Lévy walk that will indeed exhibit propagation behaviour that is somewhere in between diffusive and ballistic. We start by considering finite Lévy walks where the perturbation method applies.

4.1 General theory of finite quantum Lévy walks

Consider a one-dimensional quantum random walk with two internal degrees of freedom. The Hilbert space is $\mathcal{H} = \ell^2(\mathbb{Z}) \otimes \mathbb{C}^2$ and we consider walks that admit a coin-shift decomposition (e.g. see Theorem 4.5.2 in [2]). For $N \in \mathbb{N}$ we define the control space $\Gamma = \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$ and the set of shifts operators $\{S_n\}_{n \in \Gamma}$ acting on \mathcal{H} by $S_n = S^{bn}$ where S is the standard shift operator defined in Equation 5 and $b \in \mathbb{N}$ is a step size parameter. Since S is translation invariant with Fourier transform $S(p)$ given in Equation 9, it follows that S_n is also translation invariant with Fourier transform $S_n(p) = S(p)^n$. Given a unitary coin operator C acting solely on the internal degree of freedom, we can define the set of walks $\{\mathbf{V}_0, \mathbf{V}_1, \dots, \mathbf{V}_N\}$ such that for every $n \in \Gamma$ the walk \mathbf{V}_n is unitarily implemented by the single Kraus operator $K_n = (\mathbb{1} \otimes C) \cdot S_n \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. K_n is again translation invariant so the Fourier transform is the p -dependent multiplication operator $K_n(p) = C \cdot S_n(p)$ and we note that \mathbf{V}_n experiences no momentum transfer. At every time step, we let the probability of picking the walk \mathbf{V}_n be proportional to $1/\mathcal{A}^n$ for some $\mathcal{A} > 1$. In other words, we choose the step sizes to increase exponentially whilst the probability of picking the corresponding walks decrease exponentially. We normalize the probability distribution with $A_N = \sum_{n=0}^N 1/\mathcal{A}^n$ such that the total time evolution of an observable $n \mapsto A(n) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ is

$$(\mathbf{W}A)(\gamma) = \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \mathbf{V}_\gamma(A(n)), \quad \gamma \in \Gamma \quad (24)$$

For finite N , this defines a translation invariant and local decoherent quantum walk without momentum transfer. The only remaining assumption to check is the eigenvalue assumption with its 3 conditions. Now the probability distribution on Γ is constant in time and strictly positive, so \mathbf{W} defines a Bernoulli type decoherent walk and condition 1 is thus trivially satisfied. Condition 2 is satisfied with the choice $\bar{\rho}_p = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2}$ for every $p \in [-\pi, \pi)$. This can be verified by a straightforward computation (see Appendix H.1). Condition 3 depends on the specific choice of coin operator, so we verify it for the Hadamard coin as this is the example we consider in Section 4.2. For now we simply assume that the set of coins for which \mathbf{W} satisfies condition 3 is non-empty and that the coin C is chosen from this set.

With the assumptions satisfied, we can now use the results from the perturbation method as described in Section 3. The first step is to find the invariant state $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}$. We know that $\bar{\rho} = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2}$ is an invariant density operator for each \mathbf{V}_n for all p , so we just have to find a probability distribution $\bar{\mathbf{m}}$ that is invariant under the Markov process. Since we are considering a Bernoulli process where the probabilities are constant, this is trivially given as the initial probabilities $\bar{\mathbf{m}}_n = \frac{1}{A_N} \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n}$. We verify this explicitly in Appendix H.2. As expected, the ballistic velocity $v(p)$, Equation 18, is zero. See Lemma 9 in [1] or the explicit computation in Appendix H.2. In ballistic scaling, the sequence of characteristic functions therefore converges to the function $C(\lambda) = \text{tr } \rho_0 = 1$ and by inverse Fourier transform the corresponding sequence of ballistically scaled position random variables $\{Q_t/t\}$ converges towards the Dirac measure located at the origin. From the perturbation method, we know that the asymptotic position distribution will therefore scale diffusively and we can use Equations 21 and 22 to compute the diffusion constant

$\mu''(p)$. The point is then that the diffusion constant will depend on N and possibly diverge in the limit as N approaches infinity.

Consider Equation 22 in the context of Lévy walks. Using that C is unitary and that the shift matrices satisfy $\left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} S_n(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = i\lambda b^n \sigma_3 S_n(p)$ we find that

$$\left(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}'_0 \mathbf{1} \right) (p) = \left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} (C \cdot S_n(p))^* \mathbf{1} (C \cdot S_n(p + \varepsilon\lambda)) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} \quad (25)$$

$$= \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} S_n^*(p) \left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} S_n(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = \frac{i\lambda}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{b}{\mathcal{A}} \right)^n S_n^*(p) \sigma_3 S_n(p) \quad (26)$$

We can use that the shift matrices are diagonal and thus commute with σ_3 to cancel out S_n and S_n^* . Additionally, we know that $v = 0$, so Equation 22 for the unknown operator $X(p)$ becomes

$$X(p) - \mathbf{V}_0(X)(p) = \left(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}'_0 \mathbf{1} \right) (p) = \frac{i\lambda}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{b}{\mathcal{A}} \right)^n \sigma_3 = i\lambda \Lambda_{1,N} \sigma_3 \quad (27)$$

where we, for $k \in \mathbb{N}$, define a family of geometric series by $\Lambda_{k,N} = \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{b^k}{\mathcal{A}} \right)^n$. Differentiating the shift matrices again we get that $\left. \frac{d^2}{d\varepsilon^2} S_n(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = (i\lambda b^n)^2 S_n(p)$ and so the second derivative in Equation 21 reduces to

$$\left(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}''_0 \mathbf{1} \right) (p) = \left. \frac{d^2}{d\varepsilon^2} \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} (C \cdot S_n(p))^* \mathbf{1} (C \cdot S_n(p + \varepsilon\lambda)) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} = -\frac{\lambda^2}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathcal{A}} \right)^n \mathbf{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \quad (28)$$

With our new notation this reads $\left(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}''_0 \mathbf{1} \right) (p) = -\lambda^2 \Lambda_{2,N} \mathbf{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2}$. Using the invariant density matrix $\bar{\rho}_p = \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2}$, we can now compute the two terms in Equation 21 as

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p \left(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}''_0 \mathbf{1} \right) (p) = \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2} (-\lambda^2 \Lambda_{2,N} \mathbf{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2}) = -\lambda^2 \Lambda_{2,N} \quad (29)$$

$$2 \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p \left(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}'_0 X \right) (p) = \frac{i\lambda}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{b}{\mathcal{A}} \right)^n \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} S_n^*(p) C^* X(p) C \sigma_3 S_n(p) \quad (30)$$

$$= i\lambda \Lambda_{1,N} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} C \sigma_3 C^* X(p) \quad (31)$$

This allows us to write down the general formula for the diffusion constant $\mu''(p)$.

$$\mu''(p) = -\lambda^2 \Lambda_{2,N} + i\lambda \Lambda_{1,N} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} C \sigma_3 C^* X(p) \quad (32)$$

At this point we choose a specific coin matrix before proceeding.

4.2 Example with the Hadamard walk

The standard example for a quantum random walk is the Hadamard coin, which is defined in Equation 6. The procedure is now as follows. First we find the matrix $X(p)$ using Equation 27, then we compute the trace $\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} C \sigma_3 C^* X(p)$ and thereby the diffusion constant with Equation 32 and finally we analyze the asymptotic characteristic function with Equation 17. We aim to show that this does not converge pointwise in the limit as N approaches infinity.

We start by writing X in the Pauli basis by letting $X(p) = \sum_{i=0}^3 a_i(p) \sigma_i$. We proceed by computing the projections of both sides of Equation 27 onto each of the Pauli matrices by taking the respective Hilbert-Schmidt scalar products. This gives the set of equations

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_k^* (X - \mathbf{V}_0(X)) = i\lambda \Lambda_{1,N} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_k^* \sigma_3, \quad k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \quad (33)$$

and by writing out X in the Pauli basis this becomes

$$\sum_{i=0}^3 a_i \left(\delta_{k,i} - \frac{1}{2} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_k \mathbf{V}_0(\sigma_i) \right) = i\lambda \Lambda_{1,N} \delta_{3,k}, \quad k \in \{0, 1, 2, 3\} \quad (34)$$

Since $\mathbf{V}_0(\mathbf{1}) = \mathbf{1}$, the trace $\text{tr} \sigma_k \mathbf{V}_0(\mathbf{1}) = 0$ for $k = 1, 2, 3$, so the above equations are all independent of $a_0(p)$. This means that we can choose $a_0(p)$ freely, and thereby scale $\text{tr} X(p)$ since $\text{tr} X(p) = 2a_0(p)$. This allows us to satisfy the condition $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}(A') = 0$ by choosing $a_0 = 0$. See Appendix G.2, for why this is required. For $i, k = 1, 2, 3$, we now have to compute the trace $\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_k \mathbf{V}_0(\sigma_i)$ using the Kraus operators $K_n(p)$.

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_k (\mathbf{V}_0 \sigma_i)(p) = \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_k K_n^*(p) \sigma_i K_n(p) \quad (35)$$

$$K_n(p) = C \cdot S_n(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ipb^n} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ipb^n} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ipb^n} & e^{-ipb^n} \\ e^{ipb^n} & -e^{-ipb^n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (36)$$

Next we insert these into Equation 34 and obtain a system of 3 equations and 3 unknowns. Defining the series $s_N(p) = \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \exp(2ib^n p) / \mathcal{A}^n$, we can write the system in matrix form as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\Im(s_N(p)) & -\Re(s_N(p)) \\ 0 & 1 + \Re(s_N(p)) & -\Im(s_N(p)) \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_1 \\ a_2 \\ a_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ i\lambda \Lambda_{1,N} \end{pmatrix} \quad (37)$$

The determinant of this matrix is $1 - |s_N(p)|^2$, which we require to be non-zero in order for the inverse to exist. This is indeed the case for almost all p . We prove in Appendix H.4 that $|s_N(p)| = 1$ if and only if $p \in P = \{\frac{t\pi}{b-1} | 1 - b \leq t < b - 1, t \in \mathbb{N}\}$ for any $N \in \mathbb{N}$. P is discrete and thus a null-set with respect to the Lebesgue measure. For $p \notin P$ we can invert the matrix and solve the system of equations. Now we are only interested in the trace $\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} H \sigma_3 H^* X(p)$

where $H\sigma_3H^* = \sigma_1$. It follows that $\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} H\sigma_3H^*X(p) = \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_1X(p) = 2a_1(p)$. Hence, the solution for $a_1(p)$ alone is actually sufficient. Equation 38 gives the solution in terms of the map $f_N : [-\pi, \pi) \setminus P \mapsto \mathbb{R}$.

$$a_1(p) = i\lambda \Lambda_{1,N} (f_N(p) - 1), \quad \text{where} \quad f_N(p) = \frac{1 + \Re(s_N(p))}{1 - |s_N(p)|^2} \quad (38)$$

We can now plug this into Equation 32 to find the N -dependent diffusion constant.

$$\mu_N''(p) = -\lambda^2 (\Lambda_{2,N} + 2\Lambda_{1,N}^2 (f_N(p) - 1)) \quad (39)$$

The characteristic function is an integral over p and the set P has measure zero. This means that we can extend f_N to the full interval $[-\pi, \pi)$ by setting $f_N(p) = 0$ for $p \in P$ without altering the characteristic function. With Equations 17 and 23, we can now write down the N -dependent asymptotic characteristic function, which clearly depends on N .

$$C_N(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2\pi} e^{-\lambda^2(\frac{1}{2}\Lambda_{2,N} - \Lambda_{1,N}^2)} \int_{[-\pi, \pi)} dp e^{-\lambda^2 \Lambda_{1,N}^2 f_N(p)} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho_0(p, p) \quad (40)$$

This problem that we can only solve for μ'' outside the set P is neither surprising nor new. Similar issues arise for simple unitary walks [2]. However, it is still possible to infer the asymptotic position distribution even though it diverges at certain points (see for example the distribution for the Hadamard walk in Appendix F.2). Since we are only interested in showing the existence of decoherent quantum walks with faster than diffusive propagation behaviour, we can simply choose an initial state which allows us to disregard the points in P . Let S be a subset of $[-\pi, \pi) \setminus P$ with positive Lebesgue measure $m(S) > 0$ such that f_N is continuous and bounded on S . We show the existence of such a set in Section 4.3. In Appendix H.3, we show that for the state $\rho_0 = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ with

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{m(S)} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}} \int_S d\tilde{p} e^{-i\tilde{p}x} |x, +\rangle \quad (41)$$

the asymptotic characteristic function reduces to the well-defined expression

$$C_N(\lambda) = \frac{1}{2\pi m(S)} e^{-\lambda^2(\frac{1}{2}\Lambda_{2,N} - \Lambda_{1,N}^2)} \int_S dp e^{-\lambda^2 \Lambda_{1,N}^2 f_N(p)} \quad (42)$$

Note that while ρ_0 is a simple example to choose, it is not local and hence not physically implementable. Nevertheless, we could for example also have chosen a smooth gaussian wavepacket restricted to the set S , which would be local while achieving the same result as ρ_0 . C_N contains full information about the asymptotic position distribution and we can easily compute the first and second moments with the formula given in Appendix D.1. Since $\frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \mu_N''|_{\lambda=0} = 0$, the first moment will be $\langle x \rangle_N = -iC_N'(0) = 0$ for every $N \in \mathbb{N}$. This means that the variance will be equal to the second moment, which we find by straightforward computation to be

$$\text{Var}_N = \langle x^2 \rangle_N = -C_N''(0) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\Lambda_{2,N} - 2\Lambda_{1,N}^2 + \frac{2\Lambda_{1,N}^2}{m(S)} \int_S dp f_N(p) \right) \quad (43)$$

4.3 The infinite quantum Lévy walk

The asymptotic characteristic function and the variance of the finite quantum Lévy walk with the Hadamard coin both depends on the parameter N , which controls the largest possible jumps that the particle can perform in a single time step. The question is therefore what happens if we let N approach infinity - i.e. let the particle jump arbitrarily far with vanishing probability. The behaviour of the geometric series $\Lambda_{1,N}$ and $\Lambda_{2,N}$ depends on the ratios b/\mathcal{A} and b^2/\mathcal{A} , respectively. They will diverge whenever these are greater than or equal to 1. An important point is that $\Lambda_{2,N}$ scales faster than $\Lambda_{1,N}^2$ in the sense that $\Lambda_{2,N}/\Lambda_{1,N}^2 \propto \left(\frac{b^2}{\mathcal{A}}\right)^N \left(\frac{\mathcal{A}^2}{b^2}\right)^N = \mathcal{A}^N \rightarrow \infty$. It follows that if we can choose the set S such that f_N is bounded not only for finite N but also as N goes to infinity, then the variance in Equation 43 will diverge.

Consider $f_N(p)$ as given in Equation 38. Clearly, $\exp(2ib^n p)/\mathcal{A}^n$ is bounded by $1/\mathcal{A}^n$ for every $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Weierstrass M-test therefore implies that $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} s_N(p)$ is uniformly convergent to a function $s(p)$, which is continuous by the uniform limit theorem. Since $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} 1/\mathcal{A}_N = \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}}$, we can write $s(p)$ as

$$s(p) = \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{2ib^n p}}{\mathcal{A}^n} \quad (44)$$

It follows that both $\Re(s_N(p))$ and $|s_N(p)|^2$ are continuous in the limit as well. Additionally, we know from Appendix H.4 that $|s_N(p)|^2 \leq 1$ for any $N \in \mathbb{N}$ with equality only for $p \in P$. $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} f_N(p)$ will thus be continuous and bounded at all points where $|s(p)| < 1$. In other words, the problem reduces to showing the existence of a subset S with non-zero measure where this inequality holds. In Appendix H.4 we show that the interval $[p_1, p_2)$ with $p_1 = \frac{\pi}{4}(b-1)$ and $p_2 = \frac{3\pi}{4}(b-1)$ is an example of such a subset. This means that for $p \in [p_1, p_2)$ there exists a constant $K \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $|f_N(p)| < K$ for every $N \in \mathbb{N}$. By setting $S = [p_1, p_2)$ and inserting the lower bound $f_N(p) > -K$ into Equation 43 we find a lower bound for the variance.

$$\text{Var}_N > \frac{1}{2\pi} \left(\Lambda_{2,N} - 2\Lambda_{1,N}^2 - \frac{2\Lambda_{1,N}^2}{p_2 - p_1} \int_{[p_1, p_2)} dp K \right) = \frac{1}{2\pi} (\Lambda_{2,N} - 2(1+K)\Lambda_{1,N}^2) \quad (45)$$

As we have seen, $\Lambda_{2,N}$ scales faster than $\Lambda_{1,N}^2$ so this lower bound diverges as N goes to infinity whenever $\Lambda_{2,N}$ diverges which happens exactly when $b^2/\mathcal{A} \geq 1$. This shows that the variance of the asymptotic position distribution in diffusive scaling will diverge. The implication is that the infinite quantum Lévy walk with the Hadamard coin and the initial state ρ_0 seems to exhibit faster than diffusive propagation behaviour. The variance argument here gives the right intuition but is not actually sufficient to conclude that the position random variable, as discussed in Section 2.3, will not converge in diffusive scaling. This detail is sorted out in Appendix H.4 (Lemma 3) where we prove that the bound on f_N further implies that in the limit as $N \rightarrow \infty$, the characteristic function will have a discontinuity at the origin. The result

then follows from Lévy's continuity theorem.

It is important to note that while the arguments here provide a strong indication of faster than diffusive spreading behaviour, they cannot be considered a full proof. The infinite Lévy walks are non-local implying that the perturbation method is not technically applicable. Nevertheless, the result here motivate further study of Lévy walks and since they are still nicely represented in momentum space, a possible road is to modify the perturbation method itself allowing for some non-local walks. We tried to numerically estimate the actual scaling of Lévy walks by fitting a curve to the average variance as a function of N with the average taken over 1000 samples, but the convergence seems to be far too slow. However, we can still get an intuitive picture of how the position distributions diverges by plotting the position distribution after 1000 time steps.

Figure 1: Figures (a)-(d) show the probability distributions in diffusive scaling of finite quantum Lévy walks after 1000 time steps for different values of the jump size parameter N . The initial state is $\psi_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$

5 Conclusion

In this thesis we have studied quantum random walks as the dynamics of quantum particles in discrete time and space. Specifically, we have studied the propagation behaviour in the long

time limit of both coherent and decoherent quantum random walks.

In Section 2, we provided a detailed description of position measurements of such particles in a measure theoretic context. We showed how position measurements of a particle in any state can be represented by a probability measure and how time evolution is then represented by a sequence of such measures. This led us to the definition of the position random variables and we showed how one can infer the propagation behaviour by scaling these random variables and considering their asymptotic limit. This motivated us to find the corresponding characteristic functions as these provide a very useful tool in finding such limits.

In Section 3, we explained how to compute the long time limit of the characteristic functions using the perturbation method from [1] and [2]. The method applies to translation invariant and local quantum random walks for which the time evolution operator is best expressed in momentum space. We discussed unitarily implemented walks without momentum transfer with the main take-away being that such coherent walks will generically exhibit ballistic propagation behaviour. From here we moved on to decoherent quantum walks where we allowed for fluctuations in the choice of time evolution operator. We explained why one can apply one-parameter and finite dimensional perturbation theory as done in [2]. This decoherence generally leads to diffusive propagation behaviour although possibly around a constant drift. The implication is that in the presence decoherence quantum random walks will lose the advantage over their classical counterpart.

In Section 4, we studied quantum Lévy walks. This was motivated by numerical indications that such walks exhibit faster than diffusive propagation behaviour even though they are decoherent. We showed how the finite Lévy walk is an example of a time decoherent walk with diffusive propagation behaviour. With the perturbation method we could therefore compute the asymptotic characteristic function in diffusive scaling for standard example with the Hadamard coin. Next we considered the consequences of letting the particle jump arbitrarily far with vanishing probability and here we saw that the variance position distribution diverged. This provides analytical support for the argument that infinite quantum Lévy walks can indeed exhibit faster than diffusive propagation behaviour albeit the presence of decoherence. The next step would be to somehow guess the actual scaling of these walks as one could then perform perturbation theory in this scaling. We have tried to do this numerically, but the rate of convergence seems to be far slower than other quantum random walks. By plotting the position distribution we can nevertheless get a visual picture in Figure 1, of how the position distribution already at 1000 time steps will seem to diverge as N goes to infinity.

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A Probability measure representing position measurement

Here we prove that for any density operator $\rho \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$, the map $\mu : X \mapsto \langle P(X)|\rho \rangle_{HS} = \text{tr } P(X)\rho$ defines the unique probability measure on $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$ which satisfies the axiom in Equation 3. We start by showing that P is a projection-valued measure representing position measurements in the sense that it naturally allows us to associate a probability measure μ to each possible state ρ such that μ satisfies Equation 3. Note that \mathbb{Z}^s being countable means that P is uniquely defined by its values on the singletons $\{x\}$ and similarly, showing that a measure μ satisfy Equation 3 is sufficient to conclude that it is the unique measure representing position measurement of the state ρ (Theorem 4.1 in [6]). Consider an arbitrary set $X \in \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s)$. One can easily verify that $P(X)^* = P(X)$ and $P(X)^2 = P(X)$ and thus conclude that P maps to self-adjoint projections. Let $\{X_i\}$ be a countable partition of X . Then $P(\bigcup_i X_i) = \sum_{x \in X} |x\rangle\langle x| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}} = \sum_i \sum_{x \in X_i} |x\rangle\langle x| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}} = \sum_i P(X_i)$ where the second equality follows from the sets $\{X_i\}$ being disjoint with union X . Let $A, B \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ and consider the mapping $X \mapsto \langle P(X)A|B \rangle_{HS}$. It now follows that $\bigcup_i X_i \mapsto \langle P(\bigcup_i X_i)A|B \rangle_{HS} = \sum_i \langle P(X_i)A|B \rangle_{HS}$ implying that the map satisfies countable additivity and thus defines a complex measure on $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$. Hence, for any density operator $\rho \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$, the map $\mu : X \mapsto \langle P(X)|\rho \rangle_{HS} = \text{tr } P(X)\rho$ defines a measure. From now on let us denote the basis elements $|x\rangle \otimes |i\rangle$ by $|x, i\rangle$. By definition the projections $P(X)$ are diagonal in this basis and so the matrix elements satisfy $\langle x', i'|P(X)|x, i\rangle = \delta_{x,x'}\delta_{i,i'}\mathbf{1}_{\{x \in X\}}$. By inserting the identity $\mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{H}} = \sum_{x', i'} |x', i'\rangle\langle x', i'|$ we see that $\mu(X)$ can be expressed as

$$\mu(X) = \text{tr } \rho P(X) = \sum_{x, i} \langle x, i|\rho P(X)|x, i\rangle = \sum_{x, x', i, i'} \langle x, i|\rho|x', i'\rangle \langle x', i'|P(X)|x, i\rangle \quad (46)$$

$$= \sum_{x, x', i, i'} \langle x, i|\rho|x', i'\rangle \delta_{x,x'}\delta_{i,i'}\mathbf{1}_{\{x \in X\}} = \sum_{x \in X, i \in I} \langle x, i|\rho|x, i\rangle \quad (47)$$

As ρ is a positive semi-definite operator, the matrix elements satisfy $\langle x, i|\rho|x, i\rangle \geq 0$. Hence, μ is a real and positive measure. Finally, since $P(\mathbb{Z}^s) = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |x\rangle\langle x| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}} = \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{H}}$ and ρ is normalised, it follows that $\mu(\mathbb{Z}^s) = \text{tr } \rho = 1$ and we can conclude that μ is a probability measure on $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$ for any state ρ . It remains to show that the values of μ on singletons satisfy Equation 3. With ρ given as in Equation 1, this follows directly from Equation 46 and 47. Indeed for $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$ we can compute the measure as

$$\mu(\{x\}) = \sum_{i \in I} \langle x, i|\rho|x, i\rangle = \sum_j \lambda_j \sum_{i \in I} \langle x, i|\psi_j\rangle \langle \psi_j|x, i\rangle = \sum_j \lambda_j \sum_{i \in I} |\psi_{x,i}^j|^2 \quad (48)$$

Hence, for any state ρ the map $\mu : X \mapsto \text{tr } P(X)\rho$ is the unique probability measure on $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$ mapping subsets $X \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^s$ to the probability that a position measurement of a particle in the state ρ yields a value in X .

B The Fourier Transform

B.1 Definition

The Fourier transform will prove to be an important tool for the study of quantum random walks, so here I provide some background. We can consider elements ψ of the Hilbert space $\mathcal{H} = \ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s) \otimes \mathcal{K}$, where $\mathcal{K} \cong \mathbb{C}^d$, as functions $\psi : \mathbb{Z}^s \mapsto \mathcal{K}$. In other words, we represent the general element $\psi = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |x\rangle \otimes \psi_x$ by the function $\psi : x \mapsto \psi_x$. The Fourier transform is well-known to provide an isometry between $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s)$ and $L^2([-\pi, \pi]^s)$. Here this is generalised to vector-valued functions. The Fourier transform in Equation 49 is a map from \mathcal{H} to \mathcal{K} -valued functions on $[-\pi, \pi]^s$.

$$(\mathcal{F}\psi)(p) = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \psi_x e^{ip \cdot x} \quad (49)$$

Consider the vector space of functions of the form $\widehat{\psi} : [-\pi, \pi]^s \mapsto \mathcal{K}$ satisfying the square-integrability condition: $\frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \left\| \widehat{\psi}(p) \right\|_{\mathcal{K}}^2 < \infty$. This expression defines a semi-norm (satisfies triangle inequality, absolute scalability but not that it is only zero for the zero element) and in fact if we consider equivalence classes under this semi-norm, the expression becomes a norm and we actually have a Hilbert space [2], which will be denoted $\mathcal{L}^2(s, \mathcal{K})$ following [2]. Note that $\widehat{\psi}$ and $\widehat{\phi}$ are equivalent if they differ only on a null-set with respect to the Lebesgue measure or equivalently if $\frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \left\| \widehat{\psi}(p) - \widehat{\phi}(p) \right\|_{\mathcal{K}}^2 = 0$. The inner product on $\mathcal{L}^2(s, \mathcal{K})$ is $\langle \psi | \phi \rangle_{\mathcal{L}^2} = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \langle \psi(p) | \phi(p) \rangle_{\mathcal{K}}$.

The Fourier transform provides a unitary map between \mathcal{H} and $\mathcal{L}^2(s, \mathcal{K})$. Hence, it preserves inner products and there exists an inverse map, which is defined by Equation 50.

$$\psi_x = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p e^{-ip \cdot x} (\mathcal{F}\psi)(p) \quad (50)$$

B.2 Transforming operators

We can now expand on this and define a Fourier transform on the level of operators. For an operator $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$, the corresponding operator on $\mathcal{L}(s, \mathcal{K})$ is $\mathcal{F}A\mathcal{F}^{-1}$. As an example let $A = |\phi\rangle\langle\psi|$ and let $\eta \in \mathcal{H}$. From the unitarity of the Fourier transform we know that $\langle \psi | \eta \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} = \langle \mathcal{F}\psi | \mathcal{F}\eta \rangle_{\mathcal{L}^2}$. Hence, by applying the Fourier transform to both sides of the equation $A\eta = \langle \psi | \eta \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} \cdot \phi$ we get $(\mathcal{F}(A\eta))(p) = \langle \psi | \eta \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} (\mathcal{F}\phi)(p) = \langle \mathcal{F}\psi | \mathcal{F}\eta \rangle_{\mathcal{L}^2} (\mathcal{F}\phi)(p)$. Suppressing the \mathcal{F} we see that

$$A\eta = \langle \psi | \eta \rangle_{\mathcal{H}} \cdot \phi \iff (A\eta)(p) = \phi(p) \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' \langle \psi(p') | \eta(p') \rangle_{\mathcal{K}} \quad (51)$$

For fixed p and p' , $|\phi(p)\rangle$ is a vector in \mathcal{K} and $\langle\psi(p')|$ is a row vector (element of the dual of \mathcal{K}). Hence, $|\phi(p)\rangle\langle\psi(p')|$ is an operator on \mathcal{K} . We can therefore see that $\mathcal{F}A\mathcal{F}^{-1}$, written out in Equation 51, is an integral transform with the operator $|\phi(p)\rangle\langle\psi(p')|$ as the operator-valued integral kernel. In fact, all bounded operators can be represented on momentum space by integral operators. To show this we need Schwartz kernel theorem and a bit of background on distributions.

Distributions and Schwartz kernel theorem

Let the space $\mathcal{D}(U)$ consist of smooth test-functions with compact support defined on an open set U . An element $f \in \mathcal{D}(U)$ is therefore $C^\infty(U)$ and the set of points for which f is non-zero is a closed and bounded (compact) subset. Distributions are continuous linear functionals on $\mathcal{D}(U)$ mapping test-functions to the real numbers. The space of distributions on U is denoted $\mathcal{D}'(U)$. An example of a distribution is a mapping $f : \mathcal{D}(U) \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ with $f(g) = \int fgd x$. Say now we have a distribution k defined on $U \times U$ (or any $X \times Y$). We can then construct a linear map, K on $\mathcal{D}(U)$ by $(Kv)(y) = \int k(x, y)v(x)dx$. In fact, we can think of Kv as a distribution (i.e. a linear functional) in the sense that $\langle Kv, u \rangle = \iint k(x, y)v(x)u(y)dxdy = \langle k, u \otimes v \rangle$. In that sense, K is a linear map from $\mathcal{D}(U)$ to $\mathcal{D}'(U)$ defined via the integral kernel $k \in \mathcal{D}'(U \times U)$ and the relation $\langle Kv, u \rangle = \langle k, u \otimes v \rangle$. Schwartz kernel theorem states this is possible and that conversely, for any linear map K , there exists a unique distribution k such that $\langle Kv, u \rangle = \langle k, u \otimes v \rangle$. In other words, the theorem is that K and k satisfying this are in one-to-one correspondence.

Now just as we can represent a linear map on the space of test-functions by an integral kernel via Schwartz theorem, we can also represent a linear operator on \mathcal{H} by an operator-valued integral kernel. Hence, we can represent the Fourier transformed operator $\mathcal{F}A\mathcal{F}^{-1}$ acting on test-vectors defined on $[-\pi, \pi]^s$ (this is U) by an integral operator $A(p, p')$ for $p, p' \in [-\pi, \pi]^s$. Hence, for any $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ we can write

$$\mathcal{F}A\mathcal{F}^{-1}\psi(p) = (A\psi)(p) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' A(p, p')\psi(p') \quad (52)$$

Note the similarities to standard matrix multiplication. In fact, one can intuitively think of this as a multiplication of a "continuous" matrix $A(p, p')$ with a "continuous" vector $\psi(p')$. In other words, the p th entry in the vector $A\psi$ is given by the inner product between the p th row in A and ψ - just in higher dimensions as $p \in \mathbb{R}^s$. In a way, an operator A is a countably infinite "matrix" when acting on $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s) \otimes \mathcal{K}$ and an uncountable, but restricted to $p \in [-\pi, \pi]^s$, "matrix" when acting on $\mathcal{L}^2(s, \mathcal{K})$.

B.3 Translations

The translation operator on \mathcal{H} translates an element $\psi : y \mapsto \psi_y$ such that $(\mathcal{T}_x\psi) : y \mapsto \psi_{y-x}$ for $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}^s$. Hence, it is unitary (the inverse being \mathcal{T}_{-x} , which is indeed the transpose) and we can write it down as

$$\mathcal{T}_x = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |y - x\rangle \langle y| \otimes \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{K}} \quad (53)$$

Note that as $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s) \otimes \mathcal{K} \cong \ell^2(\mathbb{Z})^{\otimes s} \otimes \mathcal{K}$ we can split the translation and do it "coordinate wise" [2]. Translation on the level of operators can be defined similarly to how we defined the Fourier transform. We start with a translated state, we translate it back (apply inverse), apply the operator and then translate it again. This will tell us how the operator acts on translated states. In other words, for an operator A on \mathcal{H} the translation is defined by

$$\tau_x(A) = \mathcal{T}_x A \mathcal{T}_x^* \quad (54)$$

Hence, τ_x is a map from $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ into itself and we will use later that it is a homomorphism, which can be seen directly as $\tau_x(AB) = \mathcal{T}_x AB \mathcal{T}_x^* = \mathcal{T}_x A \mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{T}_x^* B \mathcal{T}_x^* = \tau_x(A) \tau_x(B)$. In other words, τ_x is an endomorphism. Translation invariant operators are not affected by τ_x for any $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$ in the sense that $\tau_x(A) = A$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$. What we will see is that such operators Fourier transform to multiplication operators. In other words, if $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ is translation invariant then the corresponding operator-valued integral kernel is "diagonal" - i.e. $A(p, p') \neq 0$ only when $p = p'$. In that case we write $\frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} A(p, p') = A(p) \delta(p - p')$ and Equation 52 becomes $(A\psi)(p) = A(p)\psi(p)$.

B.4 Translation invariance and multiplication operators

Consider first the Fourier transform of the translation operator. Let $\psi \in \mathcal{H}$. For $y \in \mathbb{Z}^s$ we have that $\psi(y) = \psi_y \in \mathcal{K}$ and $(\mathcal{T}_x \psi)(y) = \psi_{y-x}$ by application of Equation 53. From Equation 49 we know that $(\mathcal{F}\psi)(p) = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{ip \cdot y} \psi_y$ and similarly $(\mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}_x \psi)(p) = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{ip \cdot y} \psi_{y-x}$. Using that the sum is over an infinite lattice we can change variables such that

$$(\mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}_x \psi)(p) = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{ip \cdot (y+x)} \psi_y = e^{ip \cdot x} \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{ip \cdot y} \psi_y = (e^{ip \cdot x} \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) \cdot (\mathcal{F}\psi)(p) \quad (55)$$

Since ψ was arbitrarily chosen from \mathcal{H} we conclude that $\mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}_x = (e^{ip \cdot x} \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) \mathcal{F}$ and hence, the Fourier transform of the translation operator is simply $\mathcal{F}\mathcal{T}_x \mathcal{F}^{-1} = e^{ip \cdot x} \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{K}}$.

With this we can prove that multiplication operators in momentum space are translation invariant in position space. Let $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ have the multiplication operator $A(p)$ as its Fourier transform. Hence,

$$\mathcal{F}A\mathcal{F}^{-1} = A(p) \quad (56)$$

Applying the momentum space representation of the translation operator on the left side and the inverse on the right side we find

$$(e^{ip \cdot x} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) \mathcal{F} A \mathcal{F}^{-1} (e^{-ip \cdot x} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) = (e^{-ip \cdot x} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) A(p) (e^{ip \cdot x} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) \quad (57)$$

The right side of this is simply $A(p)$ since $A(p)$ commutes with the identity and thus with the momentum representation of the translation operator. For the left side we use that $\mathcal{F} \mathcal{T}_x = e^{ip \cdot x} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}} \mathcal{F}$ to commute the Fourier transform with the translation. Furthermore, this implies that the inverses satisfy $\mathcal{F}^{-1} e^{-ip \cdot x} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}} = (e^{ip \cdot x} \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}} \mathcal{F})^{-1} = (\mathcal{F} \mathcal{T}_x)^{-1} = \mathcal{T}_x^{-1} \mathcal{F}^{-1}$. Hence, we find that

$$\mathcal{F} \mathcal{T}_x A \mathcal{T}_x^{-1} \mathcal{F}^{-1} = A(p) = \mathcal{F} A \mathcal{F}^{-1} \quad (58)$$

Thus, A is translation invariant if $\mathcal{F} A \mathcal{F}^{-1}$ is a multiplication operator.

It remains to show that translation invariant operators in position space Fourier transforms to multiplication operators in momentum space. Consider a bounded translation invariant operator $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. Let $\phi_x, \psi_y \in \mathcal{K}$ and define the matrix $A_{x,y} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$ such that

$$\langle \phi_x | A_{x,y} | \psi_y \rangle = \langle x \otimes \phi_x | A | y \otimes \psi_y \rangle \quad \forall \phi_x, \psi_y \in \mathcal{K} \quad (59)$$

Translation invariance then implies that

$$\langle \phi_x | A_{x,y} | \psi_y \rangle = \langle x \otimes \phi_x | \mathcal{T}_{-y} A \mathcal{T}_{-y}^{-1} | y \otimes \psi_y \rangle = \langle x - y \otimes \phi_x | A | 0 \otimes \psi_y \rangle = \langle \phi_x | A_{x-y,0} | \psi_y \rangle \quad (60)$$

Using this we find that

$$\langle x \otimes \phi_x | A | y \otimes \psi_y \rangle = \langle x - y \otimes \phi_x | A | 0 \otimes \psi_y \rangle \quad (61)$$

$$= \langle x - y \otimes \phi_x | \mathcal{F}^* \mathcal{F} A \mathcal{F}^{-1} \mathcal{F} | 0 \otimes \psi_y \rangle e^{ip' \cdot 0} = e^{-ip \cdot (x-y)} \langle \phi_x | \mathcal{F} A \mathcal{F}^{-1} | \psi_y \rangle \quad (62)$$

Hence,

$$\langle \phi_x | \mathcal{F} A \mathcal{F}^{-1} | \psi_y \rangle = \langle \phi_x | e^{ip \cdot (x-y)} A_{x-y,0} | \psi_y \rangle \quad (63)$$

So we see here that the Fourier transformation of A only depends on p and not a second argument p' . The central point is indeed that the p' dependence disappears because $\mathcal{F} | 0 \otimes \psi_y \rangle$ is a constant (independent of p'). This completes the proof.

B.5 Transforming quantum channels

Let $A, A' \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ and let $\mathbf{W} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s})$ be translation invariant with $A' = \mathbf{W}(A)$. In momentum space we know that A and A' are represented by their integral kernels $A(p, p')$ and $A'(p, p')$, respectively. The Fourier transform of \mathbf{W} , $\mathcal{F}\mathbf{W}\mathcal{F}^*$, is therefore a map between these integral kernels. We can see the nature of this map by considering the Kraus representation of \mathbf{W} . If $\mathbf{W}(A) = \sum_{\alpha} K_{\alpha}^* A K_{\alpha}$, then the kernels satisfy $A'(p, p') = (\sum_{\alpha} K_{\alpha}^* A K_{\alpha})(p, p') = \sum_{\alpha} (K_{\alpha}^* A K_{\alpha})(p, p')$. The kernels representing composite operators are found by integrating as follows

$$A'(p, p') = \sum_{\alpha} \int d^s p'' \int d^s p''' K_{\alpha}^*(p, p'') A(p'', p''') K_{\alpha}(p''', p') \quad (64)$$

I have omitted the integration intervals, $[-\pi, \pi]^s$, and factors of $(2\pi)^s$ for a bit of simplicity, but the above seems to be the action of $\mathcal{F}\mathbf{W}\mathcal{F}^*$. In the following they will cancel naturally anyway. We know that $A(p, p') = A(p)\delta(p - p')$ and similarly for A' . Hence,

$$A'(p)\delta(p - p') = \sum_{\alpha} \int d^s p'' \int d^s p''' K_{\alpha}^*(p, p'') A(p'')\delta(p'' - p''') K_{\alpha}(p''', p') \quad (65)$$

$$= \sum_{\alpha} \int d^s p'' K_{\alpha}^*(p, p'') A(p'') K_{\alpha}(p'', p') \quad (66)$$

Thus, the multiplication operator $A'(p) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$ depends on values of $A(p'')$ at points where $p'' \neq p$. However, if we consider the case with no momentum transfer, i.e. where each Kraus operator is translation invariant and therefore has kernels of the form $K_{\alpha}(p)\delta(p - p')$, we find that

$$A'(p)\delta(p - p') = \sum_{\alpha} \int d^s p'' K_{\alpha}^*(p)\delta(p - p'') A(p'') K_{\alpha}(p'')\delta(p'' - p') \quad (67)$$

$$= \sum_{\alpha} K_{\alpha}^*(p) A(p) K_{\alpha}(p) \delta(p - p') \quad (68)$$

$$\therefore A'(p) = \sum_{\alpha} K_{\alpha}^*(p) A(p) K_{\alpha}(p) \quad (69)$$

We can now see how a translation invariant operator $\mathbf{W} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s})$, with no momentum transfer, acts in momentum space directly on the multiplication operators representing elements $A \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$, such that $(\mathbf{W}A)(p) = \mathbf{W}(p)A(p)$ where $\mathbf{W}(p)$ is the operator on $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{K})$ defined in terms of the Kraus operators as above.

C The Trace

In this section I will write down some notes concerning traces and how to take traces of operators in both position and momentum space.

C.1 Position space

Let $|\psi\rangle \in \mathcal{H}$ and write it as a general element $|\psi\rangle = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |x\rangle \otimes \psi_x$ where $|x\rangle \in \ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s)$ and $\psi_x \in \mathcal{K}$ for each $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$. The corresponding density operator is given by

$$\rho = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| = \left(\sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |x\rangle \otimes \psi_x \right) \left(\sum_{x' \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \langle x| \otimes \psi_{x'}^* \right) = \sum_{x, x' \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |x\rangle\langle x'| \otimes \psi_x \psi_{x'}^* \quad (70)$$

Note here that for every pair x, x' the expression $\psi_x \psi_{x'}^*$ is a finite dimensional matrix with dimensions $\dim \mathcal{K}$ by $\dim \mathcal{K}$. Now \mathcal{H} is a bipartite system so we can either take partial traces or the full trace. Let the sets $\{|y\rangle\}_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s}$ and $\{|i\rangle\}_{i \in \{1, \dots, \dim \mathcal{K}\}}$ form orthonormal basis' for $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s)$ and \mathcal{K} , respectively. The partial traces are then given by

$$\text{tr}_{\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s)} \rho = \sum_y (\langle y| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) \rho (|y\rangle \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathcal{K}}) = \sum_y \sum_{x, x'} \langle y|x\rangle \langle x'|y\rangle \psi_x \psi_{x'}^* = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \psi_y \psi_y^* \quad (71)$$

and

$$\text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho = \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} (\mathbb{1}_{\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s)} \otimes \langle i|) \rho (\mathbb{1}_{\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s)} \otimes |i\rangle) = \sum_{x, x'} |x\rangle\langle x'| \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \langle i| \psi_x \psi_{x'}^* |i\rangle \quad (72)$$

The full trace can now be computed by taking both partial traces simultaneously

$$\text{tr} \rho = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \langle y \otimes i | \rho | y \otimes i \rangle = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \langle i | \psi_y \psi_y^* | i \rangle = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho(y, y) \quad (73)$$

where I use the notation $\rho(x, y) = \psi_x \psi_y^*$, which comes from considering states as functions of the form $\psi : x \mapsto \psi_x$.

C.2 Momentum space

The trace is basis independent so we can derive an expression for the trace in momentum space directly from its representation in position space. First we Fourier transform the vectors $|y \otimes i\rangle$ and their duals using Equation 49.

$$(\mathcal{F}|y \otimes i\rangle)(p) = e^{ip \cdot y}|i\rangle \quad \text{and} \quad (\langle y \otimes i|\mathcal{F}^*)(p') = \langle i|e^{-ip' \cdot y} \quad (74)$$

We can now use these to rewrite Equation 73.

$$\text{tr } \rho = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \langle y \otimes i | \mathcal{F}^* \mathcal{F} \rho \mathcal{F}^{-1} \mathcal{F} | y \otimes i \rangle = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \langle i | e^{-ip' \cdot y} \mathcal{F} \rho \mathcal{F}^{-1} e^{ip \cdot y} | i \rangle \quad (75)$$

Now $e^{ip \cdot y}|i\rangle$ is an element of $\mathcal{L}^2(s, \mathcal{K})$ and we know that $\mathcal{F} \rho \mathcal{F}^{-1} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{L}^2(s, \mathcal{K}))$ can be represented by an integral kernel as in Equation 52. Hence, there exists a p, p' dependent matrix $\rho(p, p')$ such that

$$\mathcal{F} \rho \mathcal{F}^{-1} e^{ip \cdot y}|i\rangle = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' \rho(p, p') e^{ip' \cdot y}|i\rangle \quad (76)$$

So before we wrote the trace as a sum of inner products in position space. Now we convert it to inner products in momentum space. In other words, Equation 75 is a sum of inner products in $\mathcal{L}^2(s, \mathcal{K})$ between the elements $|\psi\rangle = e^{ip \cdot y}|i\rangle$ and $|\phi\rangle = \mathcal{F} \rho \mathcal{F}^{-1} e^{ip \cdot y}|i\rangle$. Note that similarly to position space I use the notation $|\psi\rangle$ for an element in the Hilbert space, which is also a map $\psi : p \mapsto e^{ip \cdot y}|i\rangle \in \mathcal{K}$. So when I write $\psi(p)$, I mean a vector in \mathcal{K} given by the map evaluated at a point p - i.e. the equivalent of how I use ψ_x in position space. Hence, we see that

$$\text{tr } \rho = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \langle \psi | \phi \rangle_{\mathcal{L}^2} = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \psi(p)^* \phi(p) \quad (77)$$

$$= \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \langle i | e^{-ip \cdot y} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' \rho(p, p') e^{ip' \cdot y} | i \rangle \quad (78)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p d^s p' \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} e^{i(p' - p) \cdot y} \sum_{i=1}^{\dim \mathcal{K}} \langle i | \rho(p, p') | i \rangle \quad (79)$$

The sum over i simply returns the trace in \mathcal{K} of the matrix $\rho(p, p')$ for a given pair p, p' . The sum over y is a delta function and here is a not so rigorous argument for that:

$$f(p) = (\mathcal{F}\mathcal{F}^{-1}f)(p) \quad (80)$$

$$f(p) = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{ip \cdot x} \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' e^{-ip' \cdot x} f(p') \quad (81)$$

$$f(p) = \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i(p-p') \cdot x} \right) f(p') \quad (82)$$

$$\therefore \delta(p-p') = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i(p-p') \cdot x} \quad (83)$$

Thus, we find that

$$\text{tr } \rho = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p d^s p' \delta(p-p') \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho(p, p') = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho(p, p) \quad (84)$$

which is an expression using only the momentum space representation of ρ . Hence, that must be the trace in momentum space. Thus,

$$\text{tr } \mathcal{F}\rho\mathcal{F}^{-1} = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho(p, p) \quad (85)$$

Now for a density operator (or just trace-class) ρ and a bounded operator A , the operator $A\rho$ will be trace-class. First we can find the corresponding integral kernel of $A\rho$:

$$(A\rho\psi)(p) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' A(p, p') (\rho\psi)(p') \quad (86)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' A(p, p') \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p'' \rho(p', p'') \psi(p'') \quad (87)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p'' \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' A(p, p') \rho(p', p'') \right) \psi(p'') \quad (88)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p'' (A\rho)(p, p'') \psi(p'') \quad (89)$$

From this we see that the integral kernel of the combined operator $A\rho$ is given by

$$(A\rho)(p, p') = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p'' A(p, p'') \rho(p'', p') \quad (90)$$

Hence, the trace of $A\rho$ can be found by plugging Equation 90 into Equation 85. Since tr_κ commutes with the integration we find that

$$\text{tr } A\rho = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p' \text{tr}_\kappa A(p, p') \rho(p', p) \quad (91)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{2s}} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p d^s p' \text{tr}_\kappa A(p, p') \rho(p', p) \quad (92)$$

If A is translation invariant then $\frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} A(p, p') = A(p) \delta(p - p')$ and the above reduces to

$$\text{tr } A\rho = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^{2s}} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p d^s p' (2\pi)^s \delta(p - p') \text{tr}_\kappa A(p) \rho(p', p) \quad (93)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \text{tr}_\kappa A(p) \rho(p, p) \quad (94)$$

D The Characteristic Function

D.1 Properties

Consider a general random variable $X : (\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu) \mapsto (\mathbb{R}^s, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s), \mu^X)$. Its characteristic function is defined by

$$C_X(\lambda) = \langle e^{i\lambda \cdot X} \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} e^{i\lambda \cdot x} d\mu^X(x), \quad \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^s \quad (95)$$

The characteristic function will be essential in studying the dynamical behaviour of quantum random walks. Hence, we will need some important results about it

1. $e^{i\lambda \cdot X} : (\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu) \mapsto (\mathbb{R}, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}))$ is measurable and bounded. As μ is a finite measure, it is also integrable i.e. $e^{i\lambda \cdot X} \in \mathcal{L}^1(\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu)$ and it follows that the characteristic function as an expectation always exists and that it is given as in Equation 95 - *Theorem 9.5 in Jacod and Protter* [6].
2. If X admits a density function it is nothing but the standard Fourier transform.
3. It is bounded and continuous as a function from \mathbb{R}^s to \mathbb{C} - *Theorem 13.1 in Jacod and Protter* [6].

4. It is in one-to-one correspondence with random variables i.e. if $C_X = C_Y$ then $X = Y$ - *Theorem 14.1 Jacod and Protter*
5. It behaves nicely under scaling. Let $\varepsilon \in \mathbb{R}$, then $C_{\varepsilon X}(\lambda) = \langle e^{i\lambda \cdot \varepsilon X} \rangle = \langle e^{i\lambda \varepsilon \cdot X} \rangle = C_X(\varepsilon \lambda)$.
6. If the moments $\langle X_1^{k_1} \cdot \dots \cdot X_s^{k_s} \rangle$ of X exists (not ∞) for all $k_i \leq K_i$ then for those k_i all partial derivatives exist and the moments obey

$$\langle X_1^{k_1} \cdot \dots \cdot X_s^{k_s} \rangle = (-i)^{k_1 + \dots + k_s} \left. \frac{\partial^{k_1 + \dots + k_s}}{\partial k_1 \dots \partial k_s} C_x(\lambda) \right|_{\lambda=0} \quad (96)$$

For the one dimensional we have that $\langle X \rangle = -iC'_X(0)$ and $\langle X^2 \rangle = -C''_X(0)$ given that the moments exist.

7. If the random variable X is supported (set where X is non-zero) on \mathbb{Z}^s , then C_X is 2π -periodic in all coordinates λ_i . This is because then $\mu^X(x) \neq 0$ only when the coordinates of x are integers.

We will be looking at the limit of the position random variable as the number of time steps approaches infinity. Hence, we need some notions of convergence of sequences of random variables. The following list provides a quick recap of the different types of convergence - see Jacod and Protter [6] for the details. Let $\{X_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of random variables. The sequence converges to X

1. *almost surely* if the set $\{\omega : \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} X_n(\omega) \neq X(\omega)\}$ has measure zero.
2. *in L^p* if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} |X_n - X|^p = 0$ provided that $X_n, X \in L^p$
3. *in probability* if for all $\varepsilon > 0$ we have $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mu(|X_n - X| > \varepsilon) = 0$
4. *in distribution or weakly* This is for when we are only interested in the probability that a random variable takes a certain value and not actually the value itself. A sequence of measures μ_n converge weakly to μ if $\int f(x) d\mu_n(x)$ converges to $\int f(x) d\mu(x)$ for any continuous and bounded function f . The random variables X_n converge in distribution to X if the corresponding pull-back measures converge weakly - i.e. if μ^{X_n} converge to μ^X .

By Lévy's continuity theorem convergence in distribution is equivalent to the characteristic functions converging pointwise. Another important property of the characteristic function, which can be seen directly from Equation 95, is that for scaled random variables εX we have $C_{\varepsilon X}(\lambda) = C_X(\varepsilon \lambda)$.

Lastly, we will be interested in computing the distribution of X directly from its characteristic function. If $C_X \in \mathcal{L}^1(\mathbb{R}^s)$ then this is simply done by taking the inverse Fourier transform. This would result in a bounded function as the integral would always be finite. However, as we will see the position distribution of unitary quantum walks have a singularity and is thus not

bounded. In that case, we will have to apply the inverse Fourier transform in a distributional sense. We will take special interest in characteristic functions of the following form

$$C_X(\lambda) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} \rho(p) \quad (97)$$

where $\rho : [-\pi, \pi]^s \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ and $v : [-\pi, \pi]^s \mapsto \mathbb{R}^s$.

D.2 Position distribution from characteristic function

Say we have a sequence of random variables $\{X_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ with $X_n : (\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu) \mapsto (\mathbb{R}^s, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s), \mu^{X_n})$ which converges in distribution to $X : (\Omega, \mathcal{A}, \mu) \mapsto (\mathbb{R}^s, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s), \mu^X)$. Let X have the characteristic function in Equation 97. For a given test-function $f \in \mathcal{D}(\mathbb{R}^s)$ the convergence implies that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int f d\mu^{X_n} = \int f d\mu^X$. If μ^X admits a density function P_X , with respect to the Lebesgue measure (here I just write $d^s x$ for the Lebesgue measure on \mathbb{R}^s) then $\int f d\mu^X = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} f(x) P_X(x) d^s x$. Even if $C_X \notin \mathcal{L}^1(\mathbb{R}^s)$ it still defines a tempered distribution which allows a Fourier transform wrt test-functions (test-functions for tempered distributions are rapidly decreasing - Schwartz functions). So we can't apply inverse Fourier transform directly but we can do it with respect to a rapidly decreasing test-function. Let \hat{f} be a test-function and consider it a Fourier transform of f - i.e. $\hat{f}(\lambda) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x e^{-i\lambda \cdot x} f(x)$. As C_X is a tempered distribution (linear functional on space of test-functions) the integral $\int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda \hat{f}(\lambda) C_X(\lambda)$ is well-defined. We can now re-write this in order to define P_X :

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda \hat{f}(\lambda) C_X(\lambda) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x e^{-i\lambda \cdot x} f(x) \right) C_X(\lambda) \quad (98)$$

$$= \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda e^{-i\lambda \cdot x} C_X(\lambda) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) P_X(x) \quad (99)$$

In other words, P_X is the function which satisfies the above for any test-function. It is the inverse Fourier transform as long as we integrate with respect to a test-function. We can now plug in the characteristic function from Equation 97 into the above and rearrange as follows

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) P_X(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda \hat{f}(\lambda) \left(\frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} \rho(p) \right) \quad (100)$$

$$= \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \rho(p) \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda \hat{f}(\lambda) e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} \quad (101)$$

The functions \hat{f} and f differ by a Fourier transform in the sense that $f(x) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda e^{i\lambda \cdot x} \hat{f}(\lambda)$. Hence, the integral over λ is simply $f(v(p))$. This can also be seen from expanding $\hat{f}(\lambda)$ with its definition

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda \widehat{f}(\lambda) e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x e^{-i\lambda \cdot x} f(x) \right) e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} \quad (102)$$

$$= \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s \lambda e^{i\lambda \cdot (v(p) - x)} = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) \delta(v(p) - x) \quad (103)$$

Inserting this in Equation 101 we obtain

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) P_X(x) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \rho(p) \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) \delta(v(p) - x) \quad (104)$$

$$= \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} d^s x f(x) \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \rho(p) \delta(v(p) - x) \quad (105)$$

Hence, we have to evaluate the integral over p , which can be done with a substitution. First of all we assume that the set of points where $\det \mathbf{J}_v(p) = 0$ (\mathbf{J} is the Jacobian) has zero Lebesgue measure such that we can remove those from the integral over p . Secondly, we split the set $[-\pi, \pi]^s$ into a sequence of subsets S_i such that v is injective on each S_i . We can then split the integral and do the substitutions separately where v can be inverted. See *Jacod and Protter - Theorem 12.6* [6] for Jacobian transformation rule.

$$\int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p \rho(p) \delta(v(p) - x) = \sum_i \int_{S_i} d^s p \rho(p) \delta(v(p) - x) \quad (106)$$

$$= \sum_i \int_{v(S_i)} d^s x' \rho(v^{-1}(x')) \delta(v(v^{-1}(x')) - x) |\det \mathbf{J}_{v^{-1}}(x')| \quad (107)$$

$$= \sum_i \mathbb{1}_{v(S_i)} \rho(v^{-1}(x)) |\det \mathbf{J}_{v^{-1}}(x)| = \sum_{q \in v^{-1}(x)} \rho(q) |\det \mathbf{J}_v(q)|^{-1} \quad (108)$$

In the last step I used that for a general non-vanishing Jacobian $\mathbf{J}_{f^{-1}} \circ f = \mathbf{J}_v^{-1}$. Hence, for points where it exists (i.e. where $\det \mathbf{J}_v(p) \neq 0$) the density P_X will be given by the following formula

$$P_X(x) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \sum_{q \in v^{-1}(x)} \rho(q) |\det \mathbf{J}_v(q)|^{-1} \quad (109)$$

In the one-dimensional case this reduces to

$$P_X(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{q \in v^{-1}(x)} \rho(q) \left| \frac{dv}{dp}(q) \right|^{-1} \quad (110)$$

E Lemmas for the perturbation method

E.1 Lemma 1 - Translation invariance of the perturbed operator

The operator $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}$ is clearly not translation invariant. In fact, $\tau_x(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}) = e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot x} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}$ and this will be the first part of this lemma. First, we consider the position operator in the position basis

$$Q = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} y |y\rangle \langle y| \otimes \mathbf{1}_\mathcal{K} \quad (111)$$

This is diagonal and so we can take the exponential (defined as a power series) simply by

$$e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot y} |y\rangle \langle y| \otimes \mathbf{1}_\mathcal{K} \quad (112)$$

It follows that the translation operator applied to this is

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_x(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}) &= \mathcal{T} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \mathcal{T}^* = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot y} \mathcal{T} |y\rangle \langle y| \mathcal{T}^* \otimes \mathbf{1}_\mathcal{K} = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot y} |y-x\rangle \langle y-x| \otimes \mathbf{1}_\mathcal{K} \\ &= \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot (y+x)} |y\rangle \langle y| \otimes \mathbf{1}_\mathcal{K} = e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot x} \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot y} |y\rangle \langle y| \otimes \mathbf{1}_\mathcal{K} = e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot x} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \end{aligned} \quad (113)$$

Despite this it turns out that $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ still commutes with the translation of operators τ_x . Given an operator $X \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ we know from the definition that $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(X) = \mathbf{W}(X e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}) e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}$. Hence,

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \circ \tau_x^{-1}(X) = \mathbf{W}(\tau_x^{-1}(X) e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}) e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \quad (114)$$

and therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
\tau_x \circ \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \circ \tau_x^{-1}(X) &= \tau_x \left(\mathbf{W} \left(\tau_x^{-1}(X) e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \right) e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \right) \\
&= \tau_x \circ \mathbf{W} \left(\tau_x^{-1}(X) e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \right) \tau_x \left(e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \right) \\
&= \mathbf{W} \circ \tau_x \left(\tau_x^{-1}(X) e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \right) e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot x} e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \\
&= \mathbf{W} \left(X e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot x} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \right) e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot x} e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \\
&= \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(X)
\end{aligned} \tag{115}$$

where we have used that τ_x is a homomorphism (as shown in Section B.3) in the second and fourth line, that \mathbf{W} commutes with translations in the third line and the linearity of \mathbf{W} in the fifth line. As X was chosen arbitrarily this shows that $\tau_x \circ \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon = \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \circ \tau_x$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$. If X is translation invariant - i.e. such that $\tau_x(X) = X$, then $\tau_x \circ \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(X) = \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \circ \tau_x(X) = \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(X)$. In other words, both \mathbf{W} and $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ maps translation invariant operators to translation invariant operators.

The set of all translation invariant and bounded operators on $\ell^2(\mathbb{Z}^s) \otimes \mathcal{K}$ is in fact a Hilbert space itself (see Lemma 3.2.4 in [2]). We can denote this subspace $\mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ and consider \mathbf{W} and $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ as maps $\mathbf{W}, \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon : \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s} \mapsto \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$. The restrictions onto this subspace are no longer related by a similarity transform. This can be seen by considering the identity. Clearly, $\mathbb{1} \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ and $\mathbf{W}(\mathbb{1}) = \mathbb{1}$. However, $\phi_\varepsilon(\mathbb{1}) = e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \notin \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$, which means that now $\phi_\varepsilon^{-1} \circ \mathbf{W} \circ \phi_\varepsilon(\mathbb{1})$ is not defined and therefore is not a representation of $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$. This implies that \mathbf{W} and $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ may now have different eigenvalues.

E.2 Lemma 2 - Momentum space representation of the perturbed operator

As an operator on $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$, the walk \mathbf{W} can be represented by a finite set of Kraus operators $\{K_i\}$ such that

$$\mathbf{W}(X) = \sum_{\alpha} K_{\alpha}^* X K_{\alpha} \tag{116}$$

This gives the following representation of the perturbed channel

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(X) = \mathbf{W} \left(A e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \right) e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} = \sum_{\alpha} K_{\alpha}^* X e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} K_{\alpha} e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \tag{117}$$

With no momentum transfer, the integral kernel representing the operator K_i is of the form $K_i(p, p') = K_i(p) \delta(p - p')$. To express Equation 117 in momentum space, we need to Fourier transform the composite operator $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} K_i e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}$. To do so we employ the methods developed in Appendix C.2. In general, for an operator represented in momentum space by

the integral kernel $A(p, p')$ we wish to find the integral kernel representing $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} A e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}$. Let $\psi = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} |x\rangle \otimes \psi_x$ be a general vector in \mathcal{H} written in the position basis. In the position basis, we know that $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} = \sum_{x' \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot x'} |x'\rangle \langle x'| \otimes \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{K}}$. Hence, $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} \psi = \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot x} |x\rangle \otimes \psi_x$ and

$$(\mathcal{F} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} \psi)(p) = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{ip\cdot y} e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot y} \psi_y = \sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}^s} e^{i(p+\varepsilon\lambda)\cdot y} \psi_y = (\mathcal{F}\psi)(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \quad (118)$$

Hence, $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}$ acts in momentum space as a translation operator and is represented by the integral kernel $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}(p, p') = (2\pi)^s \delta(p + \varepsilon\lambda - p')$ according to Equation 52. Similarly, the inverse is represented by $e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}(p, p') = (2\pi)^s \delta(p - \varepsilon\lambda - p')$. Using Equation 90 we can express the kernel of $A e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}$ as

$$(A e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q})(p, p') = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p'' A(p, p'') (2\pi)^s \delta(p'' - \varepsilon\lambda - p') \quad (119)$$

$$= A(p, p' + \varepsilon\lambda) \quad (120)$$

and similarly, we find that

$$(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} A e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q})(p, p') = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p'' (2\pi)^s \delta(p + \varepsilon\lambda - p'') A(p'', p' + \varepsilon\lambda) \quad (121)$$

$$= A(p + \varepsilon\lambda, p' + \varepsilon\lambda) \quad (122)$$

Furthermore, if A is translation invariant we know that $A(p, p') = (2\pi)^s A(p) \delta(p - p')$. Hence, the multiplication operator $A(p)$ is simply shifted such that $(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} A e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q})(p) = A(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$.

Returning to the perturbed operator, we use that K_α is assumed translation invariant to conclude that the momentum space representation of $e^{i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q} K_\alpha e^{-i\varepsilon\lambda\cdot Q}$ is exactly the shifted multiplication operator $K_\alpha(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$. It then follows from Appendix B.5 that the perturbed operator, which is translation invariant, acts in momentum space by

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(A)(p) = \sum_{\alpha} K_\alpha^*(p) A(p) K_\alpha(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \quad (123)$$

E.3 Lemma 3 - Vanishing terms of the Jordan Normal form

We consider the Jordan Normal form of the perturbed operator as given in Equation 14. We wish to show that $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \mathbf{1}_\Gamma \right)(p) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0^t(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_0(\varepsilon) (\mathbf{1}_\Gamma)$ given that the eigenvalue assumption is satisfied. From Section 3.2, we know that we can represent the perturbed operator $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ as a p -dependent matrix of dimension $(\dim \mathcal{K})^2 |\Gamma|$. We start with a quick description of

the Jordan Normal form. Any square complex matrix A , is similar to a block diagonal matrix of the form

$$J = \begin{pmatrix} J_1 & & \\ & \ddots & \\ & & J_p \end{pmatrix} \quad (124)$$

where each J_i is a square matrix of the form (called a Jordan block)

$$J_i = \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_i & 1 & & \\ & \lambda_i & \ddots & \\ & & \ddots & 1 \\ & & & \lambda_i \end{pmatrix} \quad (125)$$

The diagonal entries of J are the eigenvalues of J and therefore also of A . The geometric multiplicity of an eigenvalue λ_i is the number of Jordan blocks corresponding to λ_i . The algebraic multiplicity is the sum of the sizes of all Jordan blocks. Each Jordan block can be written as $J_i = \lambda_i \mathbf{1} + N$, where $N = \delta_{i,j-1}$ is nilpotent. If an eigenvalue λ_i is non-degenerate it follows that it only has one Jordan block and that this is $J_i = \lambda_i$. Thus, the nilpotent matrix is just 0.

At a point p , let the Jordan normal form of $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ be

$$\left(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A \right) (p) = \sum_i \left(\mu_i(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_i(\varepsilon) + \mathbf{D}_i(\varepsilon) \right) (A(p)) \quad (126)$$

Here μ_i are the ε dependent eigenvalues of $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ with the corresponding eigenprojections \mathbf{P}_i and eigennilpotent operators \mathbf{D}_i . They satisfy $\mathbf{P}_i \mathbf{P}_j = \delta_{ij} \mathbf{P}_i$ and $\mathbf{D}_i \mathbf{P}_j = \mathbf{P}_j \mathbf{D}_i = \delta_{ij} \mathbf{D}_i$. \mathbf{D}_i being nilpotent also implies that there exists $k_i \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $\mathbf{D}_i^{k_i} = 0$.

We can now use this decomposition to raise $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon$ to the t^{th} power. Using the properties of the projections and the nilpotent matrices we find that

$$\begin{aligned} \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t &= \left(\sum_i \mu_i(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_i(\varepsilon) + \mathbf{D}_i(\varepsilon) \right)^t = \sum_i \left(\mu_i(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_i(\varepsilon) + \mathbf{D}_i(\varepsilon) \right)^t \\ &= \sum_i \sum_{k=0}^t \binom{t}{k} \mu_i^{t-k}(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_i^{t-k}(\varepsilon) \mathbf{D}_i^k(\varepsilon) = \sum_i \mathbf{P}_i(\varepsilon) \sum_{k=0}^{k_i} \binom{t}{k} \mu_i^{t-k}(\varepsilon) \mathbf{D}_i^k(\varepsilon) \end{aligned} \quad (127)$$

The eigenvalue assumption

We now assume that the eigenvalue $\mu_0(0) = 1$ of the unperturbed operator is simple for almost

all p , and thus non-degenerate with the unique eigenvector $\mathbf{1}$, and that all the other eigenvalues satisfy $|\mu_i(0)| < 1$ for $i \neq 0$.

This implies that $D_0(\varepsilon) \rightarrow 0$ as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ and that $\mu_0(\varepsilon)$, $\mathbf{P}_0(\varepsilon)$ and $D_0(\varepsilon)$ are analytic in a neighbourhood around $\varepsilon = 0$ (see [2] - Lemma 3.4.2). However, we cannot guarantee that some of the other eigenvalues do not cross at $\varepsilon = 0$. If there are such degenerate eigenvalues the eigenprojections and eigennilpotents might not be analytic. In other words, we cannot use Lemma 3.4.2 of [2] on the other eigenvalues. However, we can use Lemma 3.4.3 [2]. Let the eigenvalue $\mu_i(\varepsilon)$ be degenerate and set $\varepsilon = t^{-\alpha}$ for some $\alpha \in [\frac{1}{2}, 1]$. Then the index of the corresponding nilpotent \mathbf{D}_i is greater than 1, but still finite. The operator norm of a term in the sum over k corresponding to the i^{th} term in Equation 127 is $\|\mathbf{P}_i(t^{-\alpha}) \binom{t}{k} \mu_i^{t-k}(t^{-\alpha}) \mathbf{D}_i^k(t^{-\alpha})\|$. There exists a number $n \in \mathbb{N}$, such that $\|\mathbf{P}_i(t^{-\alpha})\| = \mathcal{O}(t^{\alpha n})$ and $\|\mathbf{D}_i^k(t^{-\alpha})\| = \mathcal{O}(t^{-k\alpha n})$ (Lemma 3.4.3 [2]). Since $\binom{t}{k} = \frac{t}{k} \cdot \frac{t-1}{k-1} \dots \frac{t-(k-1)}{1} \leq \frac{t^k}{k!}$, where k is finite we see that this coefficient also scales as a finite polynomial in t . Therefore, there exists $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\|\mathbf{P}_i(t^{-\alpha}) \binom{t}{k} \mu_i^{t-k}(t^{-\alpha}) \mathbf{D}_i^k(t^{-\alpha})\| \leq \mu_i^t(t^{-\alpha}) \mathcal{O}(t^m) \quad (128)$$

If α is chosen to be $\frac{1}{2}$ or 1, m can be chosen so the above is an equality. The eigenvalue are still continuous even though it is not analytic so the condition $|\mu_i(0)| < 1$ implies that $\mu_i^t(t^{-\alpha})$ converges to zero exponentially in t . Hence, for any non-analytic eigenvalue the left side of Equation 128 will also converge to zero exponentially. If on the other hand, the eigenvalue $\mu_i(\varepsilon)$ is analytic and simple at $\varepsilon = 0$, then the index k_i is zero, the unique corresponding eigenprojection is analytic around $\varepsilon = 0$ and the only contribution from the i^{th} term in the sum in Equation 127 as we approach $\varepsilon = 0$ is $\mu_i^t(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_i(\varepsilon)$. Again the condition that $|\mu_i(0)| < 1$ implies that the limit is again zero. Thus, the only term that survives is from the eigenvalue $\mu_0(\varepsilon)$. This allows us to conclude that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon^t(\mathbf{1}) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0^t(\varepsilon) \mathbf{P}_0(\varepsilon)(\mathbf{1}) \quad (129)$$

F Unitary walks

F.1 General theory of $U(2)$ walks

Here we summarise the theory unitarily implemented quantum walks with 2 internal degrees of freedom, which again is discussed in detail in [2]. Afterwards we will apply the theory to the Hadamard walk.

A unitary quantum walk is a quantum channel represented by a single unitary Kraus operator: $\mathbf{W}(A) = W^* A W$. Here we consider translation invariant walks so W commutes with the translation operator which implies that it Fourier transforms to a multiplication operator.

In Fourier space the channel is therefore: $(\mathbf{W}A)(p) = W(p)^*A(p)W(p)$. I will consider the case where the coin space is two dimensional so $W \in U(2)$. Let $e^{i\omega_{\pm}(p)}$ be the p-dependent eigenvalues of W . Then we can write it in terms of two projections matrices, $P_+(p)$ and $P_-(p)$

$$W(p) = e^{i\omega_+(p)}P_+(p) + e^{i\omega_-(p)}P_-(p) \quad (130)$$

We know that the perturbed operator is given by $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\varepsilon}(A) = W(p)^*AW(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$. Note that we choose eigenvalues and projections such that they are analytic in ε close to $\varepsilon = 0$. In other words we have to make sure they don't intersect. We can write the spectral resolution of the perturbed operator in terms of the eigenvalues and projections above such that

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\varepsilon}^t(\mathbf{1}) = \sum_{k,l=\pm} e^{it(\omega_l(p+\varepsilon\lambda) - \omega_k(p))} P_k(p)P_l(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \quad (131)$$

As $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$, $P_k(p)P_l(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \rightarrow \delta_{kl}P_k(p)$ since P_{\pm} are orthogonal projections. Hence, only terms with $k = l$ will survive and we find that in ballistic scaling the exponent goes towards the directional derivative which here is simply $\lambda \partial_p \omega_{\pm}(p)$. Thus

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\varepsilon=\frac{1}{t}}^t(\mathbf{1}) = e^{i\lambda \partial_p \omega_+(p)}P_+(p) + e^{i\lambda \partial_p \omega_-(p)}P_-(p) \quad (132)$$

With this we can compute the characteristic function of the position distribution given an initial state ρ_0 . Note that we can do this while in Fourier space since the trace is independent of basis (cyclic).

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} C_{Q(t)/t}(\lambda) = \text{tr } \rho_0 \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_{\frac{1}{t}}^t(\mathbf{1}) = \text{tr } \rho_0 e^{i\lambda V} = C_V(\lambda) \quad (133)$$

Where V is group velocity operator given in Equation 134. This is a result of the orthogonality of the projection matrices P_{\pm} . By Levy's continuity theorem, pointwise convergence of the characteristic function is equivalent to weak convergence of the random variables (see Section D.1). Thus, the scaled position distribution converges weakly (in distribution) to the group velocity.

$$V(p) = \partial_p \omega_+(p) P_+(p) + \partial_p \omega_-(p) P_-(p) \quad (134)$$

In other words, the limit of the characteristic functions is the trace of the operator $\rho_0 e^{i\lambda V}$, which we can evaluate with Equation 94. This gives an integral of the form in Equation 97 and from this the scaled position distribution is given by Equation 110.

F.2 Example with Hadamard walk

I will now apply the above theory to an example and attempt to predict the location of peaks given the initial states. The Hadamard walk is the unitary coin-shift walk defined by the coin operator H given in Equation 6 and the shift operator given in momentum space by Equation 5 such that $\mathbf{W}(A) = [(\mathbb{1} \otimes H)S]^* A [S(\mathbb{1} \otimes H)]$.

We start by explicitly checking that this is translation invariant local. Checking locality is a bit tedious to write out but one easily see that $S|x\rangle$ only has two terms, as the sum collapses. One will be with the ket $|x+1\rangle$ and the other with the ket $|x-1\rangle$. Hence, taking the inner product with $\langle k \otimes \phi|$ will give a factor 0 whenever $k \neq x \pm 1$. The locality condition is thus fulfilled with $c = 1$. Next we check that it commutes with translations. We start by noting that it is sufficient to show that $\mathcal{T}_y S = S \mathcal{T}_y$. Indeed as the translation operators only act on the spatial degree of freedom they trivially commute with $\mathbb{1} \otimes H$ and so if they also commute with S it follows that

$$\tau_y \circ \mathbf{W}(A) = \mathcal{T}_y (\mathbb{1} \otimes H) S A S^* (\mathbb{1} \otimes H^*) \mathcal{T}_y^* = (\mathbb{1} \otimes H) S \mathcal{T}_y A \mathcal{T}_y^* S^* (\mathbb{1} \otimes H^*) = \mathbf{W} \circ \tau_y(A) \quad (135)$$

for any $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. With the definition in Appendix B.3 we can show that this is indeed the case since

$$\tau_{x'}(S) = \left(\sum_{y \in \mathbb{Z}} |y - x'\rangle \langle y| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \right) S_n \left(\sum_{y' \in \mathbb{Z}} |y' + x'\rangle \langle y'| \otimes \mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \right) \quad (136)$$

$$= \sum_{x, y, y' \in \mathbb{Z}} |y - x'\rangle \langle y|x+1\rangle \langle x|y' + x'\rangle \langle y'| \otimes |+\rangle \langle +| \quad (137)$$

$$+ |y - x'\rangle \langle y|x-1\rangle \langle x|y' + x'\rangle \langle y'| \otimes |-\rangle \langle -| \quad (138)$$

$$= \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}} |x - x' + 1\rangle \langle x - x'| \otimes |+\rangle \langle +| + |x - x' - 1\rangle \langle x - x'| \otimes |-\rangle \langle -| = S \quad (139)$$

Thus, \mathbf{W} is a translation invariant and local quantum walk. As it consists of a single Kraus operator $W = (\mathbb{1} \otimes H)S$, it follows that it exhibits no momentum transfer and the momentum space representation is therefore a multiplication operator. By Fourier transforming the Kraus operators we can express the time evolution of a translation invariant operator $A \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$ in momentum space by a p -dependent matrix product $\mathbf{W}(A)(p) = W(p)^* A(p) W(p)$. Since H only acts on the internal degree of freedom we only have to Fourier transform S . Consider a general state $\phi = \sum_{x',i} \phi_{x',i} |x'\rangle \otimes |i\rangle$. Applying S we find

$$S\phi = \sum_{x,x'} \phi_{x',1}|x+1\rangle\langle x|x'\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \phi_{x',0}|x-1\rangle\langle x|x'\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \quad (140)$$

$$= \sum_x \phi_{x,1}|x+1\rangle \otimes |1\rangle + \phi_{x,0}|x-1\rangle \otimes |0\rangle \quad (141)$$

$$\therefore (\mathcal{F}S\phi)(p) = \sum_x \phi_{x,1}e^{ip(x+1)}|1\rangle + \phi_{x,0}e^{-ip(x-1)}|0\rangle \quad (142)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} (\mathcal{F}\phi)(p) \quad (143)$$

It follows that

$$S(p) = \mathcal{F}S\mathcal{F}^* = \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (144)$$

Thus the matrix $W(p)$ is given by

$$W(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & e^{-ip} \\ e^{ip} & -e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (145)$$

This has the eigenvalues $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}i \sin(p) \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}\sqrt{1 + \cos^2(p)}$. As they have modulus 1 we can write them as $e^{i\omega_{\pm}(p)}$ where $\omega_{\pm}(p)$ are the arguments of the eigenvalues given by

$$\omega_{\pm}(p) = \frac{\pi}{2} \pm \arccos\left(\frac{\sin p}{\sqrt{2}}\right) \quad (146)$$

Differentiating these dispersion relations gives the velocities

$$\partial_p \omega_{\pm}(p) = \mp \frac{\cos(p)}{\sqrt{1 + \cos^2(p)}} \quad (147)$$

Next we can find the eigenvectors and from these the diagonalization of W . Let M denote the matrix which columns are the eigenvectors of W . Then M and it's inverse are given as in Equation 149.

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_+} + e^{-ip} & \sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_-} + e^{-ip} \\ e^{ip} & e^{ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (148)$$

$$M^{-1} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(e^{i\omega_+} - e^{i\omega_-})} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -\sqrt{2}e^{i(\omega_- - p)} - e^{-2ip} \\ -1 & \sqrt{2}e^{i(\omega_+ - p)} + e^{-2ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (149)$$

With these we can write down the spectral resolution of W as

$$W(p) = M^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\omega_+} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{i\omega_-} \end{pmatrix} M \quad (150)$$

$$= e^{i\omega_+} M^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} M + e^{i\omega_-} M^{-1} \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} M \quad (151)$$

$$= e^{i\omega_+} P_+(p) + e^{i\omega_-} P_-(p) \quad (152)$$

where the projections are given by

$$P_+(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(e^{i\omega_+} - e^{i\omega_-})} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_+} + e^{-ip} & e^{-ip} \\ e^{ip} & -\sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_-} - e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (153)$$

$$P_-(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(e^{i\omega_+} - e^{i\omega_-})} \begin{pmatrix} -\sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_-} - e^{-ip} & -e^{-ip} \\ -e^{ip} & \sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_+} + e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (154)$$

With the velocities and the projections computed we have the group velocity operator V , and we are ready to compute the $\text{tr} \rho_0 e^{i\lambda V}$ for a given initial state. First we note the translation invariance of $e^{i\lambda V}$ as it is a multiplication operator by construction of the quantum channel \mathbf{W} . Hence, the trace is given by the formula in Equation 94. With an initial state such as $\psi(p) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$, we can write down the density matrix, $\rho_0(p, p') = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$. As this density matrix is independent of p and p' , we can suppress those and simply write ρ_0 . The limiting characteristic function is now given by

$$C_V(\lambda) = \text{tr} \rho_0 e^{i\lambda V} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{[-\pi, \pi)} dp \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} e^{i\lambda V(p)} \rho_0 \quad (155)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{[-\pi, \pi)} dp \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \left(e^{i\lambda \partial_p \omega_+(p)} P_+(p) + e^{i\lambda \partial_p \omega_-(p)} P_-(p) \right) \rho_0 \quad (156)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{[-\pi, \pi)} dp e^{i\lambda \partial_p \omega_+(p)} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} P_+(p) \rho_0 + e^{i\lambda \partial_p \omega_-(p)} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} P_-(p) \rho_0 \quad (157)$$

With the projection operators and the density matrix the computation of the traces are straightforward:

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho_0 P_+ = \text{tr} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(e^{i\omega_+} - e^{i\omega_-})} \begin{pmatrix} \sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_+} + e^{-ip} & e^{-ip} \\ e^{ip} & -\sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_-} - e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (158)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\cos(p)}{\sqrt{1 + \cos^2(p)}} \right) \quad (159)$$

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho_0 P_- = \text{tr} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}(e^{i\omega_+} - e^{i\omega_-})} \begin{pmatrix} -\sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_-} - e^{-ip} & -e^{-ip} \\ -e^{ip} & \sqrt{2}e^{i\omega_+} + e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (160)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\cos(p)}{\sqrt{1 + \cos^2(p)}} \right) \quad (161)$$

Hence, we find that

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho_0 P_{\pm} = \frac{1}{2} (1 + \partial_p \omega_{\pm}(p)) \quad (162)$$

We see now that C_V is the sum of two integrals of the form considered in Equation 97 with $v(p) = \partial_p \omega_{\pm}(p)$ and $\rho(p) = \frac{1}{2} (1 + \partial_p \omega_{\pm}(p))$, respectively. Hence, we can find the scaled position distribution with the formula from Equation ???. First we find the peaks - i.e. where the formula is not valid. We differentiate the velocities:

$$\partial_p^2 \omega_{\pm}(p) = \pm \frac{\sin(p)}{(1 + \cos^2(p))^{\frac{3}{2}}} \quad (163)$$

which is equal to zero if and only if $\sin(p) = 0$ which for $p \in [-\pi, \pi)$ is realised at $p \in \{-\pi, 0\}$. Here the velocities are $\partial_p \omega_{\pm}(p) = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ so the scaled position distribution will peak at these points, which also happen to be the extremas of the ranges of the velocities. Hence, the scaled

position distribution will have asymptotes there and we can compute the formula will give the function for all values $x \in (-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$. The first step in computing this function is to find the pre-images of the velocities. For $x \in (-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$ we find that

$$\partial_p \omega_+^{-1}(x) = \left\{ \pm \arccos \left(\frac{-x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \right) \right\} \quad (164)$$

$$\partial_p \omega_-^{-1}(x) = \left\{ \pm \arccos \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{1-x^2}} \right) \right\} \quad (165)$$

The scaled position distribution is now

$$P_V(x) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{s=\pm} \sum_{q \in \partial_p \omega_s^{-1}(x)} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho_0 P_s(q) |\partial_p^2 \omega_s(q)|^{-1} \quad (166)$$

For $q \in \partial_p \omega_+^{-1}(x)$ we can compute the two terms

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho_0 P_+(q) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 - \frac{\cos(q)}{\sqrt{1+\cos^2(q)}} \right) = \frac{1}{2}(1+x) \quad (167)$$

$$|\partial_p^2 \omega_+(q)|^{-1} = \left| \frac{\sin(q)}{(1+\cos^2(q))^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right|^{-1} = \frac{1}{1-x^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-2x^2}} \quad (168)$$

and similarly for $q \in \partial_p \omega_-^{-1}(x)$ we also find that

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho_0 P_-(q) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{\cos(q)}{\sqrt{1+\cos^2(q)}} \right) = \frac{1}{2}(1+x) \quad (169)$$

$$|\partial_p^2 \omega_-(q)|^{-1} = \left| \frac{\sin(q)}{(1+\cos^2(q))^{\frac{3}{2}}} \right|^{-1} = \frac{1}{1-x^2} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-2x^2}} \quad (170)$$

Hence, combining these

$$P_V(x) = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{1}{1-x} \frac{1}{\sqrt{1-2x^2}}, \quad x \in \left(-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \quad (171)$$

Figure 2: Plot of the numerical scaled position distribution for the Hadamard walk after 1000 time steps with the initial state $\psi(p) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$. The red curve is the analytical limit given by Equation 171

Figure 3: Plot of the numerical scaled position distribution for the Hadamard walk after 10^4 time steps with the initial state $\psi(p) = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$ except each point is the average of the values at the 20 nearest positions. In other words, at a point $x \in (-\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}, \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}})$, the blue plot is not the scaled position distribution at x but the average of the values of the scaled position distribution at the 20 nearest points to x . The red curve is the analytical limit given by Equation 171

Let $W_2(p)$ and $W_3(p)$ be defined as follows

$$W_2(p) = C_2 S(p) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & \sqrt{3} \\ -\sqrt{3} & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & \sqrt{3}e^{-ip} \\ -\sqrt{3}e^{ip} & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (172)$$

$$W_3(p) = C_3 S(p) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & i \\ i & 1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & 0 \\ 0 & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & ie^{-ip} \\ ie^{ip} & e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad (173)$$

As before the dispersion relations are given by the arguments of the eigenvalues.

$$\omega_{2,\pm} = \pm \arccos \left(\frac{\cos(p)}{2} \right) \quad (174)$$

$$\omega_{3,\pm} = \pm \arccos \left(\frac{\cos(p)}{\sqrt{2}} \right) \quad (175)$$

Differentiating these we find the velocities

$$\partial_p \omega_{2,\pm}(p) = \pm \frac{\sin(p)}{\sqrt{4 - \cos^2(p)}} \quad (176)$$

$$\partial_p \omega_{3,\pm}(p) = \pm \frac{\sin(p)}{\sqrt{2 - \cos^2(p)}} \quad (177)$$

The stationary points in both cases are located at $p = \frac{\pi}{2}$. Hence, for localised initial states the peaks of the scaled position distribution will be at the points $\partial_p \omega_{2,\pm}(\pi/2) = \pm 1/2$ for the walk defined by the C_2 coin and at $\partial_p \omega_{3,\pm}(\pi/2) = \pm 1/\sqrt{2}$ for the walk defined by the coin C_3 . In Figure 4 we can see that indeed these peaks correspond to the numerical values.

Figure 4: Figures (a)-(c) show the scaled position distributions after 300 time steps of walks using the coin matrices H , C_2 and C_3 , respectively. The black dashed lines are located at the analytically calculated peak locations, which are $1/\sqrt{2}$ for (a), $1/2$ for (b) and $1/\sqrt{2}$ for (c).

F.3 Convergence rates and targeting specific velocities

As an interesting detail we can consider how fast the velocity of the position distribution converges towards the limiting velocities from the dispersion relations. For a given walk let the limiting velocity be v . As a distance measure we can use the probability of the particle having absolute position larger than vt , which is $\text{Prob}(|Q|) > vt$, for any time t . Figure 5 show these

probabilities as functions of time for the 3 walks. We can clearly see the exponential rate of convergence.

Figure 5: Figures (a)-(c) show the probability of the particle having velocity larger than the limiting velocities as a function of time for each of the three walks defined by the coin operators H , C_2 and C_3 , respectively. The limiting velocities are given by $v_1 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, $v_2 = \frac{1}{2}$ and $v_3 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, as shown in Section ???. Exponential fit functions are also plotted

In section I explained how one could target specific velocities with sharply peaked initial states. The python script "Targeting p's with gaussians" is an implementation of this idea. The code implements a walks in Fourier space given an initial state and then transforms the final state back to position space. By choosing a narrow gaussian with non-zero mean as the initial state we can target specific p values. Note that the initial state is only spin-up. Let the mean be $p = \pi/4$ and the standard deviation 0.1. For the 3 walks, the analytical velocities are then

$$\partial_p \omega_{1,\pm} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) = \pm \frac{\cos(\frac{\pi}{4})}{\sqrt{1 + \cos^2(\frac{\pi}{4})}} = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (178)$$

$$\partial_p \omega_{2,\pm} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) = \pm \frac{\sin(\frac{\pi}{4})}{\sqrt{4 - \cos^2(\frac{\pi}{4})}} = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{7}} \quad (179)$$

$$\partial_p \omega_{3,\pm} \left(\frac{\pi}{4} \right) = \pm \frac{\sin(\frac{\pi}{4})}{\sqrt{2 - \cos^2(\frac{\pi}{4})}} = \pm \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \quad (180)$$

Figure 6 shows that these values do indeed correspond to the location of the peaks in the scaled position distribution.

Figure 6: Figures (a)-(c) show the scaled position distribution after 300 time steps for the unitary walks defined by the coin matrices H , C_2 and C_3 , respectively. The initial state in all cases were $\psi_0(p) = \begin{pmatrix} \psi_+(p) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$ where $\psi_+(p)$ is a gaussian distribution with mean $\pi/4$ and standard deviation 0.1. The dotted lines are located at $\pm 1/\sqrt{3}$ in (a), $\pm 1/\sqrt{7}$ in (b) and $\pm 1/\sqrt{3}$ in (c). They show the locations of the analytical peaks based on the velocities in Equations 178-180

G Decoherent quantum walks

G.1 Preliminaries

Here we extend the arguments from Section 2 to decoherent quantum walks. We wish to again obtain a sequence of random variables that represent position measurements such that we can find the long time limit via the characteristic functions. As in Section 2 the work we have done here is inspired by but independent of [1] and [2]. We start by time evolving in the Schrödinger picture and then later change to the Heisenberg picture, exactly as in Section 2. We introduce a control process which at each time step picks an element γ from the finite and discrete index set Γ and apply an associated time evolution operator \mathbf{T}_γ . The process is Markovian so the probabilities depend only on the previous time step. We initialise this process by picking an initial state from a set of density operators $\{\rho_{0,\alpha}\}_{\alpha \in \Gamma}$ with the associated probabilities $\{p_0(\alpha)\}_{\alpha \in \Gamma}$. We know from Section 2.2 that, given a state ρ , the probability of a position measurement yielding a value in $X \subseteq \mathbb{Z}^s$ is equal to $\text{tr } P(X)\rho$. This added uncertainty as to which density operator is the initial state means that the same probability is now a sum over possible measurements multiplied by their probabilities such that

$$\text{Prob}_{t=0}(x \in X) = \sum_{\alpha} p_0(\alpha) \text{tr } P(X)\rho_{0,\alpha} \quad (181)$$

The time evolution is a combination of this Markovian control process and the application of the chosen time evolution operator. Let the probability that the index $\beta \in \Gamma$ is picked given that $\alpha \in \Gamma$ was chosen at the previous time step be denoted by $p(\beta|\alpha)$. In other words, we apply \mathbf{T}_β to the density operator $\rho_{0,\alpha}$ with probability $p(\beta|\alpha)$. The probability of measuring a value $x \in X$ at time $t = 1$ is again a sum over all possibilities for what the control process picks multiplied by their respective probabilities. Clearly,

$$\text{Prob}_{t=1}(x \in X) = \sum_{\beta} \sum_{\alpha} p(\beta|\alpha)p_0(\alpha) \text{tr } P(X)\mathbf{T}_\beta(\rho_{0,\alpha}) \quad (182)$$

As time progresses further, these probabilities will get very complicated. This motivates us to redefine our system (i.e. how we represent states, observables and time evolution) in such a way to simplify these and preserve these probabilities while making it possible to go through a similar analysis as in Section 2 and obtain the correct sequence of characteristic functions. A natural way to do this is to think of states as bounded maps $\eta \mapsto \rho(\eta)$ for $\eta \in \Gamma$ such that $\rho(\eta)$ is a positive trace-class operator. We normalize the map such that $\sum_{\eta} \text{tr } \rho(\eta) = 1$. Indeed, we can think of the initial state as the map $\rho_0 : \alpha \mapsto p_0(\alpha)\rho_{0,\alpha}$ and since each $\rho_{0,\alpha}$ is a density operator and $p_0(\alpha)$ are probabilities, this clearly satisfies $\sum_{\alpha} \text{tr } p_0(\alpha)\rho_{0,\alpha} = \sum_{\alpha} p_0(\alpha) = 1$. In other words, we let states be represented by elements of the combined Hilbert space $\ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ consisting of bounded maps from Γ to $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ under the operator norm

$\|A\|_{op'} = \sup_{\alpha \in \Gamma} \|A(\alpha)\|_{op}$. We can now model time evolution as an operator acting on this space. We can define it pointwise as

$$(\mathbf{T}A)(\beta) = \sum_{\alpha} p(\beta|\alpha) \mathbf{T}_{\beta}(A(\alpha)) \quad (183)$$

First we have to show that the total time evolution operator \mathbf{T} will indeed map states to states in the sense that $\mathbf{T}(\rho)$ is still a bounded map from Γ to the set of positive trace-class operators with $\sum_{\beta} \text{tr}(\mathbf{T}\rho)(\beta) = 1$. Each of the operators \mathbf{T}_{β} are quantum channels and therefore linear, trace-preserving and completely positive maps on $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. Hence, each $\mathbf{T}_{\beta}(\rho(\alpha))$ is again positive and trace-class with $\text{tr} \mathbf{T}_{\beta}(\rho(\alpha)) = \text{tr} \rho(\alpha)$. Since, the probabilities $p(\beta|\alpha)$ are non-negative with $\sum_{\alpha} p(\beta|\alpha) \leq 1$, the sum $(\mathbf{T}\rho)(\beta) = \sum_{\alpha} p(\beta|\alpha) \mathbf{T}_{\beta}(\rho(\alpha))$ will be a bounded, positive and trace-class operator. Lastly, we can check that normalisation is satisfied.

$$\sum_{\beta} \text{tr}(\mathbf{T}\rho)(\beta) = \sum_{\beta} \sum_{\alpha} p(\beta|\alpha) \text{tr} \mathbf{T}_{\beta}(\rho(\alpha)) \quad (184)$$

$$= \sum_{\alpha} \left(\sum_{\beta} p(\beta|\alpha) \right) \text{tr} \rho(\alpha) = \sum_{\alpha} \text{tr} \rho(\alpha) = 1 \quad (185)$$

The third inequality follows from $\sum_{\beta} p(\beta|\alpha) = 1$ for all $\alpha \in \Gamma$, which is simply stating that the probability to pick any walk, given that the walk associated with α was picked at the previous time step, is indeed 1. This shows that under the new definition of states and time evolution, the time evolution will map states to states as it should. Let us quickly note that the position probabilities can be expressed as

$$\text{Prob}_{t=0}(x \in X) = \sum_{\alpha} \text{tr} P(X) \rho_0(\alpha) \quad (186)$$

and

$$\text{Prob}_{t=1}(x \in X) = \sum_{\beta} \text{tr} P(X) (\mathbf{T}\rho_0)(\beta) \quad (187)$$

This can be extended, by induction, to all time steps $t \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$\text{Prob}_t(x \in X) = \sum_{\beta} \text{tr} P(X) (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0)(\beta) \quad (188)$$

This definition of time evolution is indeed a Markov process defined by the probabilities $p(\cdot|\cdot) : \Gamma \times \Gamma \mapsto \mathbb{R}_+$, which we can arrange in a matrix of dimension $|\Gamma|$. The process is

initialised by the vector with entries $p_0(\alpha)$.

With a general expression for the probabilities at all time steps we can now construct the corresponding probability measures and from there define a sequence of probability measures just as in Section 2.2. Once again we consider the measure space $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$ and define the time dependent map $\bar{\mu}_t : X \mapsto \sum_{\beta} \text{tr} P(X) (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta)$. In Section 2.2 we showed that for all $A, B \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ the map $X \mapsto \langle P(X)A|B \rangle_{HS} = \text{tr} A^* P(X) B$ defines a complex measure on $(\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s))$. The question is therefore whether or not the sum of operators $\sum_{\beta} (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta)$ is bounded under the standard operator norm for all $t \in \mathbb{N}$. Let $t \in \mathbb{N}$. As explained the map \mathbf{T} is an endomorphism on the set of states and thus $(\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta)$ is positive and trace-class with $\text{tr} (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta) \leq 1$ and therefore bounded with $\|(\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta)\|_{op} \leq 1$. Hence, $\sup_{\beta \in \Gamma} \|(\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta)\|_{op} \leq 1$ and as Γ is finite it follows that $\sum_{\beta} (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ and thus $\bar{\mu}_t$ is indeed a complex measure. Additionally, we know that $(\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta)$ is positive semi-definite for all β and thus $\bar{\mu}_t$ is a real and positive measure, exactly as in Section 2. By our normalisation condition on states $\bar{\mu}_t(\mathbb{Z}^s) = \sum_{\beta} \text{tr} \mathbf{1}_{\mathcal{H}} (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta) = 1$ so $\bar{\mu}_t$ is again a probability measure.

We now define the sequence of position random variables $\{\bar{Q}_t\}_{t \in \mathbb{N}}$ such that $\bar{Q}_t : (\mathbb{Z}^s, \mathcal{P}(\mathbb{Z}^s), \bar{\mu}_t) \mapsto (\mathbb{R}^s, \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{R}^s), \bar{\mu}_t^{\bar{Q}_t})$ with $\bar{Q}_t(x) = x$ for all $x \in \mathbb{Z}^s$. This allows us to consider the scaled characteristic functions. By the same considerations as in Section 2.3, with $\sum_{\beta} (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta)$ substituted for ρ_t , we find that

$$C_{\varepsilon \bar{Q}_t}(\lambda) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^s} e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot x} d\bar{\mu}_t^{\bar{Q}_t} = \sum_{\beta} \text{tr} e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q} (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta) = \sum_{\beta} \langle (\mathbf{T}^t \rho_0) (\beta) | e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q} \rangle_{HS} \quad (189)$$

At this point we wish to change to the Heisenberg picture and time evolve the unitary operator $e^{i\varepsilon \lambda \cdot Q}$ instead of ρ_0 . To do so we start by defining the natural extension of the Hilbert-Schmidt inner product to our new space $\ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ as

$$\langle A|B \rangle_{dec} = \sum_{\alpha} \langle A(\alpha)|B(\alpha) \rangle_{HS} \quad (190)$$

for any $A, B \in \ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. Since Γ is finite, $\langle \cdot | \cdot \rangle_{dec}$ clearly defines an inner product on $\ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. We can therefore define the adjoint of \mathbf{T} as the unique bounded operator \mathbf{W} on $\ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ satisfying $\langle \mathbf{T}(A)|B \rangle_{dec} = \langle A|\mathbf{W}(B) \rangle_{dec}$ for all $A, B \in \ell^\infty(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. The map \mathbf{W} will have the same structure in the sense that it also consists of two steps - one picking from a set of time evolutions and the other updating the probabilities according to a Markovian process. We denote the time evolution operators by \mathbf{V}_γ for $\gamma \in \Gamma$ and note that they are the adjoint operators of \mathbf{T}_γ , but applied in the opposite order such that $(\mathbf{T}_\beta \circ \mathbf{T}_\alpha)^* = \mathbf{V}_\beta \circ \mathbf{V}_\alpha$ - i.e. we are interchanging the indices as well. This is a result of transposing the Markov process. We end up with an operator of the form

$$(\mathbf{W}A)(\gamma) = \sum_{\eta \in \Gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \mathbf{V}_{\eta}(A(\eta)), \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma \quad (191)$$

where we will take each \mathbf{V}_{γ} to be a translation invariant and local quantum random walk and the numbers $\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta}$ are non-negative with $\sum_{\eta} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} = 1$. With this we can change to the Heisenberg picture and write the characteristic function as

$$C_{\varepsilon\bar{Q}_t}(\lambda) = \langle \mathbf{T}^t(\rho_0) | e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q} \rangle_{dec} = \langle \rho_0 | \mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q}) \rangle_{dec} \quad (192)$$

$$= \sum_{\gamma} \langle p_0(\gamma) \rho_{0,\gamma} | (\mathbf{W}^t e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q})(\gamma) \rangle_{dec} = \sum_{\gamma} p_0(\gamma) \text{tr} \rho_0 (\mathbf{W}^t e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q})(\gamma) \quad (193)$$

where we in the last equality fix the initial states as the same density matrix $\rho_{0,\gamma} = \rho_0 \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ for all $\gamma \in \Gamma$. Hence, the initial probabilities $p_0(\gamma)$ simply serves the purpose of initialising the Markov process. In general we will choose these to be an invariant vector for the Markov process. When time evolving in the Heisenberg picture we can equivalently describe states as linear functionals on the space of observables (i.e. elements of the dual space or bra space in physics terms). Following the notation of [1] and [2] we can write a state as the map $\mathbf{m} \otimes \rho : A \mapsto \sum_{\gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma} \text{tr} \rho A(\gamma)$ such that the characteristic functions takes the form

$$C_{\varepsilon\bar{Q}_t}(\lambda) = \mathbf{m} \otimes \rho_0 (\mathbf{W}^t(e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q})) = \sum_{\gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma} \text{tr} \rho_0 (\mathbf{W}^t e^{i\varepsilon\lambda \cdot Q})(\gamma) \quad (194)$$

To illustrate how the time evolution works in action we consider the simple case where the control process picks from a set of three walks $\{\mathbf{V}_1, \mathbf{V}_2, \mathbf{V}_3\}$. We let the Markov process be a permutation on this set. We can arrange the probabilities $\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta}$ in a matrix, which updates the probability distribution at each time step with a simple matrix vector multiplication. In the permutation Markov process this is

$$\mathbf{M} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (195)$$

We can initialize the Markov process with a vector in \mathbb{R}^3 , for example the uniform distribution given by $\frac{1}{3}(1, 1, 1)^T$. Given $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ we now consider the map $\gamma \mapsto A(\gamma) = \frac{1}{3}A$ or equivalently $\mathbf{A} = \frac{1}{3}(A, A, A)^T$ as an element of $\mathcal{L}^{\infty}(\Gamma) \otimes \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$. The time evolution now follows

$$\mathbf{W}(\mathbf{A}) = \frac{1}{3} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{V}_1(A) \\ \mathbf{V}_2(A) \\ \mathbf{V}_3(A) \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{W}^2(\mathbf{A}) = \frac{1}{3} \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{V}_1(\mathbf{V}_3(A)) \\ \mathbf{V}_2(\mathbf{V}_1(A)) \\ \mathbf{V}_3(\mathbf{V}_2(A)) \end{pmatrix} \quad (196)$$

Clearly, this will return to the coherent scheme as it is periodic but we could for example where it has a small probability of using the same walk again instead of permuting.

G.2 Solving for the first and second order of $\mu_0(\varepsilon)$

The perturbed operator is given as in Section 3.2 by

$$\left(\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A\right)(\gamma) = \sum_{\eta \in \Gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma,\varepsilon}(A(\eta)), \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma \quad (197)$$

Note that we have suppressed the p -dependence since the point is that we do the perturbation theory for fixed p . We consider the eigenvalue equation $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A_\varepsilon = \mu_\varepsilon A_\varepsilon$ where as $\varepsilon \rightarrow 0$ we have that $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon \rightarrow \mathbf{W}$, $A_\varepsilon \rightarrow \mathbf{1}$ and $\mu_\varepsilon \rightarrow 1$. As explained everything in this equation is analytic in ε so we can expand in orders of ε .

$$\widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma,\varepsilon} = \mathbf{V}_\gamma + \varepsilon \widetilde{\mathbf{V}}'_\gamma + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \widetilde{\mathbf{V}}''_\gamma + \mathbf{O}(\varepsilon^3) \quad (198)$$

$$A_\varepsilon = \mathbf{1} + \varepsilon A' + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} A'' + \mathbf{O}(\varepsilon^3) \quad (199)$$

$$\mu_\varepsilon = 1 + \varepsilon \mu' + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \mu'' + \mathbf{O}(\varepsilon^3) \quad (200)$$

First order

Collecting terms of first order in ε we get the equation

$$\sum_{\eta \in \Gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \left(\mathbf{V}_\gamma(A'(\eta)) + \widetilde{\mathbf{V}}'_\gamma(\mathbf{1}) \right) = \mu' \mathbf{1} + A'(\gamma), \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma \quad (201)$$

which can be rewritten to

$$(\mathbf{W}A')(\gamma) - A'(\gamma) = \mu' \mathbf{1} - \widetilde{\mathbf{V}}'_\gamma(\mathbf{1}), \quad \forall \gamma \in \Gamma \quad (202)$$

using that the sum over η of $\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta}$ equals 1. From Proposition 4.5.12 in [2] we know that there exists an invariant state for \mathbf{W} for almost all p which we can call $\overline{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \overline{\rho}_p$. By invariant state we mean a p -dependent linear functional $\overline{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \overline{\rho}_p : A(p) \mapsto \sum_\gamma \overline{\mathbf{m}}_\gamma \text{tr}_K A(\gamma, p)$ for which

$\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p(\mathbf{W}(A)) = \bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p(A)$. In fact, in the finite dimensional case $\bar{\mathbf{m}}$ is simply the stationary distribution (eigenvector with eigenvalue 1) of the matrix \mathbf{M} with entries $\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta}$ and $\bar{\rho}_p$ is the normalized density matrix which is proportional to the identity operator, since \mathbf{W} is unital. Taking expectations on both sides makes the left side go to zeros and the expectation of $\mathbf{1}$ is 1. Hence, we find that

$$\mu'(p) = \bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p \left(\tilde{\mathbf{V}}'(\mathbf{1})(p) \right) \quad (203)$$

With Lemma 2 in Appendix E.2 we know that $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_{\gamma,\varepsilon}(\mathbf{1})(p) = \sum_{\alpha} K_{\gamma,\alpha}^*(p) K_{\gamma,\alpha}(p + \varepsilon\lambda)$. Hence,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{V}}'_{\gamma}(\mathbf{1})(p) = \sum_{\alpha} K_{\gamma,\alpha}^*(p) \left. \frac{d}{d\varepsilon} K_{\gamma,\alpha}(p + \varepsilon\lambda) \right|_{\varepsilon=0} \quad (204)$$

$$= \lambda \cdot \sum_{\alpha} K_{\gamma,\alpha}^*(p) \nabla K_{\gamma,\alpha}(p) \quad (205)$$

Applying $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}$ to the map $\gamma \mapsto \tilde{\mathbf{V}}'_{\gamma}(\mathbf{1})$, we find that

$$\mu'(p) = \sum_{\gamma} \bar{\mathbf{m}}_{\gamma} \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \bar{\rho} \tilde{\mathbf{V}}'_{\gamma}(\mathbf{1}) \quad (206)$$

$$= \lambda \cdot \sum_{\gamma} \sum_{\alpha} \bar{\mathbf{m}}_{\gamma} \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \bar{\rho}(p, p) K_{\gamma,\alpha}^*(p) \nabla K_{\gamma,\alpha}(p) \quad (207)$$

If we define the function $v(p)$ such that

$$v(p) = -i \sum_{\gamma} \sum_{\alpha} \bar{\mathbf{m}}_{\gamma} \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \bar{\rho}(p, p) K_{\gamma,\alpha}^*(p) \nabla K_{\gamma,\alpha}(p) \quad (208)$$

then we can write μ' as

$$\mu'(p) = i\lambda \cdot v(p) \quad (209)$$

If $\mu' \neq 0$ then we can now see that $\mu_0(\varepsilon)^t = (1 + \varepsilon\mu' + o(\varepsilon^2))^t$. In ballistic scaling we set $\varepsilon = \frac{1}{t}$ and thus $\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \mu_0(1/t)^t = \left(1 + \frac{\mu'(p)}{t} + o\left(\frac{1}{t^2}\right)\right)^t = e^{\mu'(p)}$. Inserting this into the characteristic function as given in Equation 17 with some initial state ρ_0 we get

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} C_{Q_t/t}(\lambda) = \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \text{tr} \rho_0 \widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon(\mathbf{1}) = \frac{1}{(2\pi)^s} \int_{[-\pi, \pi]^s} d^s p e^{i\lambda \cdot v(p)} \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho_0(p, p) \quad (210)$$

and from this we can infer the position distribution with Equation 110.

Second order

If the scaled position distribution Q_t/t is sharply peaked around a constant v , we can study its behaviour around this point on the \sqrt{t} scale by considering $(Q_t - vt)/\sqrt{t}$. We will consider the case where $v(p)$ is constant in p .

Expanding the eigenvalue equation $\widetilde{\mathbf{W}}_\varepsilon A_\varepsilon = \mu_\varepsilon A_\varepsilon$ again and collecting terms of second order in ε we find that

$$\sum_{\eta \in \Gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma, \eta} \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma''(\mathbf{1}) + 2\widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma'(A'(\eta)) + \mathbf{V}_\gamma(A''(\eta)) \right) = \mu'' \mathbf{1} + 2\mu' A'(\gamma) + A''(\gamma) \quad (211)$$

As in the first order case we can rewrite this as follows

$$(\mathbf{W}A'')(\gamma) - A''(\gamma) = \mu'' \mathbf{1} + 2\mu' A'(\gamma) - \sum_{\eta \in \Gamma} \mathbf{m}_{\gamma, \eta} \left(\widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma''(\mathbf{1}) + 2\widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma'(A'(\eta)) \right) \quad (212)$$

The eigenvector A_ε is only determined up to a factor. Hence, we can choose to scale it such that $\overline{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \overline{\rho}_p(A_\varepsilon) = 1$. As an example, we do this explicitly for the quantum Lévy walk with the Hadamard coin in Section 4.2. This implies that

$$1 = \overline{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \overline{\rho}_p \left(\mathbf{1} + \varepsilon A' + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} A'' + o(\varepsilon^3) \right) \quad (213)$$

$$= 1 + \varepsilon \overline{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \overline{\rho}_p(A') + \frac{\varepsilon^2}{2} \overline{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \overline{\rho}_p(A'') + \overline{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \overline{\rho}_p(o(\varepsilon^3)) \quad (214)$$

The expectation of the term $2\mu' A'$, where we are considering the second order of ε , must therefore be zero. Thus we are left with

$$\mu''(p) = \sum_{\gamma} \overline{\mathbf{m}}_\gamma \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \overline{\rho}_p \widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma''(\mathbf{1})(p) + 2 \sum_{\gamma} \sum_{\eta} \overline{\mathbf{m}}_\gamma \mathbf{m}_{\gamma, \eta} \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \overline{\rho}_p \widetilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma'(A'(\eta, p))(p) \quad (215)$$

Here we need to find A' with the first order equation.

G.3 Bernoulli walks

A Bernoulli type walk is characterized by having a constant probability distribution on the control space. The rows in \mathbf{M} are all equal and they sum to 1. Hence, $\mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} = \mathbf{m}_\eta = \bar{\mathbf{m}}_\eta$. Let $X(p) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_\eta A'(\eta, p)$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0 = \sum_\gamma \bar{\mathbf{m}}_\gamma \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma$. The unperturbed version (where $\varepsilon = 0$) is still denoted without the tilde, so $\mathbf{V}_0 = \sum_\gamma \bar{\mathbf{m}}_\gamma \mathbf{V}_\gamma$. Then we can write Equation 215 as

$$\mu''(p) = \text{tr}_\kappa \bar{\rho}_p \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0''(\mathbf{1})(p) + 2 \text{tr}_\kappa \bar{\rho}_p \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0'(X(p))(p) \quad (216)$$

By the definition of time evolution, we know that

$$(\mathbf{W}A')(\gamma) = \sum_\eta \mathbf{m}_{\gamma,\eta} \mathbf{V}_\gamma(A'(\eta)) = \sum_\eta \bar{\mathbf{m}}_\eta \mathbf{V}_\gamma(A'(\eta)) = \mathbf{V}_\gamma(X) \quad (217)$$

Hence, Equation 202 implies that

$$A'(\gamma) = \mathbf{V}_\gamma(X) - \mu' \mathbf{1} + \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma'(\mathbf{1}) \quad (218)$$

By taking the average with respect to the stationary distribution, we obtain an equation for X .

$$X = \sum_\gamma \mathbf{m}_\gamma A'(\gamma) = \sum_\gamma \mathbf{m}_\gamma \left(\mathbf{V}_\gamma(X) - \mu' \mathbf{1} + \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_\gamma'(\mathbf{1}) \right) \quad (219)$$

$$= \mathbf{V}_0(X) - i\lambda \cdot v \mathbf{1} + \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0'(\mathbf{1}) \quad (220)$$

In conclusion, we can determine the second derivative of the eigenvalue from the equations

$$\mathbf{V}_0(X)(p) - X(p) = i\lambda \cdot v(p) \mathbf{1} - \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0'(\mathbf{1})(p) \quad (221)$$

and

$$\mu''(p) = \text{tr}_\kappa \bar{\rho}_p \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0''(\mathbf{1})(p) + 2 \text{tr}_\kappa \bar{\rho}_p \tilde{\mathbf{V}}_0'(X(p))(p) \quad (222)$$

H Lévy walks

H.1 The eigenvalue assumption

Here we check that the time evolution operator \mathbf{W} for the Hadamard quantum Lévy walk satisfies the eigenvalue assumption using Prop. 4.5.12 (see Section 3.2 for the 3 conditions on \mathbf{W}). We have already seen that condition 1 is trivially satisfied. Condition 2 is generally satisfied for all quantum Lévy walks with time evolution operator as given in Equation 24. To see this we pick the density operator $\bar{\rho}_p = \frac{1}{2}\mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2}$, which obviously has non-zero eigenvalues. Let $A \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{C}^2)$ and $\gamma \in \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$. The following computation shows that $\bar{\rho}_p$ is indeed an invariant state.

$$\mathrm{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p (\mathbf{V}_\gamma A)(p) = \frac{1}{2} \mathrm{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \mathbb{1} (\mathbf{V}_\gamma A)(p) = \frac{1}{2} \mathrm{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} K_n^*(p) A K_n(p) \quad (223)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \mathrm{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} K_n^*(p) A K_n(p) = \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \mathrm{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \frac{1}{2} A = \mathrm{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \frac{1}{2} A = \mathrm{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p A \quad (224)$$

Next we check that condition 3 is satisfied for the Lévy walk with the Hadamard coin. The Kraus operators are

$$K_n(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ipb^n} & e^{-ipb^n} \\ e^{ipb^n} & -e^{-ipb^n} \end{pmatrix} \quad (225)$$

where $n \in \{0, 1, \dots, N\}$. We wish to show that for almost all p there exists an $r \in \mathbb{N}$ such that the set of possible matrix products $K_{n_1} K_{n_2} \cdots K_{n_r}$ is irreducible and with the identity in their linear span. One way to do this is find 4 linearly independent matrices from the set of possible products. This would imply that the linear span of the set is in fact the whole space of 2×2 matrices and it would follow that it includes the identity and that the set is irreducible. We show here that the matrices $K_0(p)$, $K_1(p)$, $K_0(p)K_1(p)$ and $K_1(p)K_0(p)$ are linearly independent for almost all p - i.e. we allow them to be linearly dependent on a measure zero set. First let us write them out

$$K_0(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip} & e^{-ip} \\ e^{ip} & -e^{-ip} \end{pmatrix} \quad K_1(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ipb} & e^{-ipb} \\ e^{ipb} & -e^{-ipb} \end{pmatrix} \quad (226)$$

$$K_0(p)K_1(p) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip(b+1)} + e^{ip(b-1)} & e^{-ip(b-1)} - e^{-ip(b+1)} \\ e^{ip(b+1)} - e^{ip(b-1)} & e^{-ip(b-1)} + e^{-ip(b+1)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (227)$$

$$K_1(p)K_0(p) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} e^{ip(b+1)} + e^{-ip(b-1)} & e^{ip(b-1)} - e^{-ip(b+1)} \\ e^{ip(b+1)} - e^{-ip(b-1)} & e^{ip(b-1)} + e^{-ip(b+1)} \end{pmatrix} \quad (228)$$

To show that they are linearly independent, we map each matrix onto the dimensional vector with the same entries. Then we arrange these 4 dimensional vector in a 4×4 matrix A and compute the determinant, which we require to be non-zero the the vectors, and thus their corresponding 2×2 matrices, to be linearly independent. This is a little messy on paper, but can easily be implemented in Mathematica or Python. The resulting determinant is

$$\det(A) = -\frac{1}{2}e^{-3ip(b+1)} (e^{6ip} - e^{ip(2b+4)} - e^{ip(4b+2)} + e^{6ibp}) \quad (229)$$

Solving for $\det(A) = 0$, we find that this is only true for $p = 0$, $p = -\pi/(b-1)$ and $p = -\pi/(2b-2)$. Hence, we can conclude that condition 3 is indeed satisfied for almost all p for every $N \in \mathbb{N}$.

H.2 Invariant state and ballistic scaling

First we verify that the state

$$\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p : A(p) \mapsto \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \left(\frac{\mathbb{1}_{\mathbb{C}^2}}{2} \right) A(n, p) \quad (230)$$

is indeed an invariant state of the time evolution operator \mathbf{W} (Equation 24). We already know that $\bar{\rho}_p$ is an invariant density operator for every \mathbf{V}_n for almost all p and this is used in the third equality below. Take an arbitrary translation invariant operator $A \in \mathcal{T}_{\mathcal{K},s}$. We have to show that $\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p (\mathbf{W}(A)(p)) = \bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p (A(p))$ for almost all p .

$$\bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p(\mathbf{W}(A)) = \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \left(\frac{1}{A_N \mathcal{A}^\gamma} \right) \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{1}{A_N \mathcal{A}^n} \right) \mathbf{V}_\gamma(A(n, p))(p) \quad (231)$$

$$= \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \left(\frac{1}{A_N \mathcal{A}^\gamma} \right) \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{1}{A_N \mathcal{A}^n} \right) \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p \mathbf{V}_\gamma(A(n, p))(p) \quad (232)$$

$$= \sum_{\gamma=0}^N \left(\frac{1}{A_N \mathcal{A}^\gamma} \right) \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{1}{A_N \mathcal{A}^n} \right) \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p A(n, p) \quad (233)$$

$$= \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{1}{A_N \mathcal{A}^n} \right) \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p(A(n, p)) = \bar{\mathbf{m}} \otimes \bar{\rho}_p(A(p)) \quad (234)$$

With the invariant state in place, we can compute the velocity in ballistic scaling with Equation 18. We use that that $\frac{d}{dp}K_n(p) = ib^n \sigma_1 K_n(p)$ and that K_n is unitary for every $n \in \Gamma$. Hence,

$$v(p) = -i \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \bar{\rho}_p K_n^*(p) \frac{d}{dp} K_n(p) \quad (235)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{b}{\mathcal{A}} \right)^n \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} K_n^*(p) \sigma_1 K_n(p) \quad (236)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \left(\frac{b}{\mathcal{A}} \right)^n \text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \sigma_1 = 0 \quad (237)$$

H.3 Targeting momenta with the initial state

Here we describe how to choose an initial state ρ in position space that targets a specific range of momenta when Fourier transformed. Specifically, we wish to limit the momenta to the subset $S \subset [-\pi, \pi)$ with the non-zero Lebesgue measure $m(S) > 0$, in the sense that, for any measurable function g the expectation in momentum space reduces so $\int_{[-\pi, \pi)} dp g(p) \text{tr}_{\mathcal{K}} \rho(p, p) = \int_S dp g(p)$. We will use this state in our analysis of the quantum Lévy walks, so it is sufficient for us to consider the one-dimensional case with $\mathcal{K} = \mathbb{C}^2$. We use the notation $|x, \pm\rangle$ for the basis vector $|x\rangle \otimes |\pm\rangle$

We postulate that the state $\rho = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi|$ where

$$|\psi\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m(S)}} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}} \int_S d\tilde{p} e^{-i\tilde{p}x} |x, +\rangle \quad (238)$$

will pick out the momenta in S this way. Firstly, we show that this is indeed normalized. With the ket given above, the state and its trace are given by

$$\rho = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| = \frac{1}{m(S)} \sum_{x,x' \in \mathbb{Z}} \int_S \int_S d\tilde{p}d\tilde{p}' e^{-i(\tilde{p}x - \tilde{p}'x')} |x, +\rangle\langle x', +| \quad (239)$$

$$\text{tr } \rho = \sum_{x'' \in \mathbb{Z}, s = \pm} \langle x'', s | \rho | x'', s \rangle = \frac{1}{m(S)} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}} \int_S \int_S d\tilde{p}d\tilde{p}' e^{-i(\tilde{p} - \tilde{p}')x} \quad (240)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m(S)} \int_S \int_S d\tilde{p}d\tilde{p}' \delta(\tilde{p} - \tilde{p}') = \frac{1}{m(S)} \int_S d\tilde{p} 1 = \frac{m(S)}{m(S)} = 1 \quad (241)$$

In momentum space the state ρ is represented by the integral kernel $\mathcal{F}\rho\mathcal{F}^*(p, p') = |\psi(p)\rangle\langle\psi(p')|$, which we can consider a p -dependent complex matrix in two dimensions. The bra-ket notation becomes a bit cumbersome at this point, so we change and write the states as maps to \mathbb{C}^2 instead whilst keeping the basis $|\pm\rangle$. The Fourier transform of the ket in Equation 238 and the state ρ , which is the outer product with itself, are given by

$$(\mathcal{F}\psi)(p) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{m(S)}} \sum_{x \in \mathbb{Z}} e^{ipx} \int_S d\tilde{p} e^{-i\tilde{p}x} |+\rangle \quad (242)$$

$$\rho(p, p') = \frac{1}{m(S)} \sum_{x, x' \in \mathbb{Z}} \int_S \int_S d\tilde{p}d\tilde{p}' e^{i(p-\tilde{p})x} e^{-i(p'-\tilde{p}')x'} |+\rangle\langle +| \quad (243)$$

From this we see that

$$\text{tr}_{\mathbb{C}^2} \rho(p, p) = \frac{1}{m(S)} \sum_{x, x' \in \mathbb{Z}} \int_S \int_S d\tilde{p}d\tilde{p}' e^{i(p-\tilde{p})x} e^{-i(p-\tilde{p}')x'} \quad (244)$$

$$= \frac{1}{m(S)} \int_S d\tilde{p} \delta(p - \tilde{p}) \quad (245)$$

As g is measurable the desired result now follows since

$$\int_{[-\pi, \pi]} dp g(p) \frac{1}{m(S)} \int_S d\tilde{p} \delta(p - \tilde{p}) = \frac{1}{m(S)} \int_S dp g(p) \quad (246)$$

In Section 4.2, we wish to employ this result to reduce the characteristic function given in Equation 40 to the expression in 42. We have now shown that with the choice of ρ_0 above, this follows if the map $p \mapsto \exp(-\lambda^2 \Lambda_{1,N}^2 f_N(p))$ is measurable on $[-\pi, \pi]$. The argument for this is as follows. Firstly, the composition of two measurable functions is measurable. Hence, we only have to show that $f_N : [-\pi, \pi] \mapsto \mathbb{R}$ is measurable. Note that we consider the same extension of f_N as in Section 4.2 - i.e. for the singularity points $p \in P$ we set $f_N(p) = 0$. Now the family of sets $\{(a, \infty) | a \in \mathbb{R}\}$ generate the Borel σ -algebra on \mathbb{R} . To show that f_N is measurable we therefore only have to show that for every $a \in \mathbb{R}$ the set $A = \{p \in [-\pi, \pi] | f_N(p) > a\}$ is a Borel set. We know that $f_N(p)$ is continuous everywhere except at the points in the discrete set P . This implies that the set $B = \{p \in [-\pi, \pi] \setminus P | f_N(p) > a\}$ is open and thus Borel. By

re-writing B as $B = \{p \in [-\pi, \pi) | f_N(p) > a\} \cap ([-\pi, \pi) \setminus P)$ it is clear that $A = B \cup P$ if $a < 0$ whilst $A = B$ if $a \geq 0$. As the set P is discrete it is closed and therefore also Borel. Since the union of two Borel sets is itself Borel, we conclude that A is always Borel. This shows that f_N is indeed measurable and it follows that we can use the result in Equation 246 to reduce $C_N(\lambda)$ to an integral over S as done in Section 4.2.

H.4 Lemmas for quantum Lévy walks

Lemma 1. $|s_N(p)| = 1$ if and only if $p \in P$ for every $N \in \mathbb{N}$.

Here we consider the function $s_N(p)$ where

$$s_N(p) = \frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{e^{2ib^n p}}{\mathcal{A}^n} \quad (247)$$

and we wish to proof that the modulus of this is only equal to 1 for points $p \in P$ where

$$P = \left\{ \frac{t\pi}{b-1} \mid 1-b \leq t < b-1, t \in \mathbb{N} \right\} \quad (248)$$

The modulus in question is

$$|s_N(p)| = \left(\frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{\cos(2b^n p)}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{1}{A_N} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{\sin(2b^n p)}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right)^2 \quad (249)$$

Let us define the terms

$$lhs = \left(\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{\cos(2b^n p)}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right)^2 + \left(\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{\sin(2b^n p)}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right)^2 \quad (250)$$

$$rhs = \left(\frac{1}{A_N} \right)^2 = \left(\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right)^2 \quad (251)$$

We wish that $lhs = rhs$ only for $p \in P$. Let us expand both terms and collect terms with the same order of $1/\mathcal{A}$.

$$lhs = 1 + \frac{2}{\mathcal{A}} + \dots + \frac{N+1}{\mathcal{A}^N} + \frac{N}{\mathcal{A}^{N+1}} + \dots + \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^{2N}} = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{n+1}{\mathcal{A}^n} + \sum_{n'=N+1}^{2N} \frac{2N-n'+1}{\mathcal{A}^{n'}} \quad (252)$$

Hence, the coefficient of the general term $1/\mathcal{A}^n$ is $n+1$ for $0 \leq n \leq N$ and $2N-n'+1$ for

$N < n' \leq 2N$. The cosine sum on the left hand side expands to

$$\left(\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{\cos(2b^n p)}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right)^2 = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \cos(2b^k p) \cos(2b^{n-k} p) \right) \quad (253)$$

$$+ \sum_{n=N+1}^{2N} \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} \left(\sum_{k=n-N}^N \cos(2b^k p) \cos(2b^{2N-n-k} p) \right) \quad (254)$$

and equivalently for the sine sum. By collecting terms with the same order we find that the coefficient of $1/\mathcal{A}^n$ when $n \leq N$ for *lhs* is

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \cos(2b^k p) \cos(2b^{n-k} p) + \sin(2b^k p) \sin(2b^{n-k} p) = \sum_{k=0}^n \cos(2(b^k - b^{n-k}) p) \quad (255)$$

while the coefficient $1/\mathcal{A}^{n'}$ when $n' > N$ is

$$\sum_{k'=n'-N}^N \cos\left(2\left(b^{k'} - b^{2N-n'-k'}\right) p\right), \quad N < n' \leq 2N \quad (256)$$

Now we notice that everyone of these coefficients are smaller than or equal to the coefficients of *rhs*. This gives us a necessary and sufficient condition on p for $lhs = rhs$ to be satisfied.

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \cos(2(b^k - b^{n-k}) p) \leq \sum_{k=0}^n 1 = n + 1 \quad (257)$$

$$\sum_{k'=n'-N}^N \cos\left(2\left(b^{k'} - b^{2N-n'-k'}\right) p\right) \leq \sum_{k'=n'-N}^N 1 = 2N - n' + 1 \quad (258)$$

Clearly, (257) is only an equality when $\cos(2(b^k - b^{n-k}) p) = 1$ for every $n \in \{0, \dots, N\}$ and $k \in \{0, \dots, n\}$. We call this condition 1. Similarly, (258) is only an equality when $\cos(2(b^{k'} - b^{2N-n'-k'}) p) = 1$ for every $n' \in \{N + 1, \dots, 2N\}$ and $k' \in \{n' - N, \dots, N\}$ and we call this condition 2. These two conditions on p are necessary and sufficient for $lhs = rhs$ and thus for $|s(p)| = 1$. If one of them is not met then lhs will be strictly smaller than rhs whilst if both are met all coefficients in the expansions are equivalent and they will be equal. We will now proof that the points $p \in P$ are the only ones satisfying this. Note that the set of points for which $lhs = rhs$ is non-empty as it includes $p = 0$. Let p' be a point in this set. By condition 1 we know that that $\cos(2(b^k - b^{n-k}) p') = 1$ for $n \leq N$ and $k \leq n$. Fix $k = n = 1$ such that $\cos(2(b-1)p') = 1$. Hence, $2(b-1)p' \in 2\pi\mathbb{Z}$ and by definition $p' \in [-\pi, \pi)$. This shows that $p' \in P$. To show the other way we start by letting $p \in P$ and write it as $p = \pi - \frac{t\pi}{b-1}$ where $t \in \{0, 1, \dots, 2(b-1)\}$. Let us check condition 1 by choosing any n and k as described. We wish to show that $2(b^k - b^{n-k})p$ is a multiple of 2π . If $n = 2k$ then this is trivially satisfied.

Assume first that $n > 2k$ and factor out b^k . Then

$$2(b^k - b^{n-k})p = 2b^k(1 - b^{n-2k})p = -2b^k(b-1)(b^{n-2k-1} + b^{n-2k-2} + \dots + 1) \left(\pi - \frac{t\pi}{b-1} \right) \quad (259)$$

$$= -2\pi [b^k(b^{n-2k-1} + b^{n-2k-2} + \dots + 1)(b-1-t)] \in 2\pi\mathbb{Z} \quad (260)$$

If $n < 2k$, we can factor b^{n-k} out instead and with the same argument show that again $2(b^k - b^{n-k})p \in 2\pi\mathbb{Z}$. Thus, condition 1 is indeed satisfied. In fact, we can follow the same procedure to check condition 2. There we consider $2(b^{k'} - b^{2N-n'-k'})p$ and pick the larger of k' and $2N - n' - k'$. By factoring out b raised to this, we are similarly left with a polynomial of the form $b^a - 1$ and since this has $b - 1$ as a factor, we can conclude that the whole expression is a multiple of 2π such that condition 2 is satisfied. This shows that $lhs = rhs$ for every point $p \in P$ and it now follows that $|s_N(p)| = 1$ if and only if $p \in \mathbb{P}$ for every $N \in \mathbb{N}$.

Lemma 2. $|s(p)| < 1$ for $p \in [p_1, p_2)$ with $p_1 = \frac{\pi}{4}(b-1)$ and $p_2 = \frac{3\pi}{4}(b-1)$.

We start by extracting the first two terms.

$$\begin{aligned} |s(p)| &= \left| \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{e^{2ib^n p}}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right| \leq \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \left| e^{2ip} + \frac{e^{2ipb}}{\mathcal{A}} \right| + \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \left| \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{e^{2ib^n p}}{\mathcal{A}^n} \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \left| 1 + \frac{e^{2ip(b-1)}}{\mathcal{A}} \right| + \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^n} = \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \left| 1 + \frac{e^{2ip(b-1)}}{\mathcal{A}} \right| + 1 - \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (261)$$

Now the complex number $z(p) = 1 + e^{2ip(b-1)}/\mathcal{A}$ will lie on the circle in the complex plane with center 1 and radius $1/\mathcal{A}$. The point on this circle with the smallest modulus is the intersection with the real axes closest to the origin. As $\frac{1}{\mathcal{A}} < 1$, this follows from the triangle inequality. We can thus minimize $|z(p)|$ by choosing p such that $2p(b-1) = \pi$. This choice of p is not surprising as it lies exactly in the middle between two consecutive points in the set P . This motivates the choice

$$S = \left[\frac{\pi}{4(b-1)}, \frac{3\pi}{4(b-1)} \right) \quad (262)$$

For $p \in S$, the modulus $|z(p)|$ is largest at the boundary point $p' = \frac{\pi}{4(b-1)}$. Hence, if we can use the inequality from 261 to show that $|s(p')| < 1$, then it follows that $|s(p)| < 1$ for every $p \in S$. One can see this by considering the complex plane

Figure 7: Illustration to show why the choice of p' maximises the modulus.

Since $\exp(2ip'(b-1)) = \exp(i\frac{\pi}{2}) = i$, the inequality for p' reads

$$|s(p')| \leq \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \sqrt{1 + \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^2}} + 1 - \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}} \left(1 + \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}}\right) = \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}^2} \sqrt{\mathcal{A}^2 + 1} + \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^2} \quad (263)$$

$$< \frac{(\mathcal{A}-1)\mathcal{A}}{\mathcal{A}^2} + \frac{1}{\mathcal{A}^2} = 1 - \frac{\mathcal{A}-1}{\mathcal{A}^2} < 1 \quad (264)$$

Lemma 3. The limit as $N \rightarrow \infty$ of the sequence of asymptotic characteristic functions $C_N(\lambda)$ will have a discontinuity at the origin.

For $N \in \mathbb{N}$ we consider the asymptotic characteristic function as given in Equation 42 with $S = [p_1, p_2]$ as in Section 4.3. We saw in Section 4.3 that the sequence of functions $\{f_N\}_{N \in \mathbb{N}}$ can be uniformly bounded on S by a constant K . This implies that $-\lambda^2 \Lambda_{1,N}^2 f_N(p) < K \lambda^2 \Lambda_{1,N}^2$ for every $p \in [p_1, p_2]$ and it follows that

$$C_N(\lambda) = \frac{e^{-\lambda^2(\frac{1}{2}\Lambda_{2,N} - \Lambda_{1,N}^2)}}{2\pi(p_2 - p_1)} \int_{[p_1, p_2]} dp e^{-\lambda^2 \Lambda_{1,N}^2 f_N(p)} \quad (265)$$

$$< \frac{e^{-\lambda^2(\frac{1}{2}\Lambda_{2,N} - \Lambda_{1,N}^2)}}{2\pi(p_2 - p_1)} \int_{[p_1, p_2]} dp e^{K\lambda^2 \Lambda_{1,N}^2} = \frac{1}{2\pi} e^{-\lambda^2(\frac{1}{2}\Lambda_{2,N} - (1+K)\Lambda_{1,N}^2)} \quad (266)$$

The expression in Equation 265 is positive for all $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ so it follows that $C_N(\lambda) \geq 0$ for every $N \in \mathbb{N}$. For the upper bound we use that $\Lambda_{2,N}/\Lambda_{1,N}^2 \rightarrow \infty$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$. This implies that the bound in Equation 266 converges to 0 for every $\lambda \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ whenever $\Lambda_{2,N}$ diverges. By the Squeeze theorem, we conclude that $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} C_N(\lambda) = 0$ when $\lambda \neq 0$ and $b^2/\mathcal{A} > 1$. Since $C_N(0) = \text{tr } \rho_0 = 1$ for every $N \in \mathbb{N}$, this will also hold in the limit. Hence, the limit of $C_N(\lambda)$ is 1 for $\lambda = 0$ and 0 everywhere else. This is clearly not continuous at the origin and so it follows

from Lévy's continuity theorem that the corresponding sequence of position random variables with diffusive scaling will *not* converge in distribution. With the definitions in Section 2.3, the implication is indeed that the propagation behaviour of the infinite quantum Lévy walk with the Hadamard coin is *not* diffusive.